

SPACE AND FORM MAKING:
THE AGIKUYU RESTATEMENT

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This thesis is submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements of Bachelor of Architecture at the University of Nairobi.

*To my mother,
Mrs. Rosebella Bor*

DECLARATION

I, Bor Carolyne Chelimo, hereby declare that this thesis is my original work. This document has not been submitted in any other academic institution for the award of any degree. Any sources used have been referenced as instructed.

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All my lecturers,

For the 6 years.

CHAPTER ONE:
INTRODUCTION

Fig 1.01; A map showing the different locations of ethnic groups in Kenya. Source: www.kenyanize.co.ke retrieved in October 2019.

Fig 1.08; Image showing a modern Kikuyu woman with face paintings, jewel and ornamental. Source: www.arco-images.com retrieved in October 2019.

1.1 Background of the problem

The Agikuyu (Fig 1.02) boasts as the largest ethnic group among the forty-two tribes with an estimate of about 17% of the total Kenyan population in accordance to the 2009 census. Owing their history to the Bantu group of community, they are related to other ethnic groups such as the Embu, Mbeere, Meru, Kamba, among other Northeast bantu sub-groups. They are highly concentrated around the Central region of Kenya (Fig 1.01), the Mount Kenya region, where they believed that *Ngai* (God) reigned. It was in this mountain that he called forth Agikuyu, the father of the Agikuyu people. He then sent him to a cluster of fig trees where he met Mumbi (considered the mother of the Agikuyu) and solidified this place as sacred, commonly identified as Mukurwe wa Nyagathanga in Murang'a County (Fig 1.03). It is considered the origin of the Agikuyu people. The name derives its meaning to the Mukurwe tree viewed as a religious object of worship and Nyagathanga as the bird that builds its nest and resides on the Mukurwe tree (Rukwaro, 2016). During the colonial area, the religious centre was destroyed by the British government in order to incapacitate the Agikuyu people spiritually. It is no question that people in the olden days held religion to the highest regard. Order ensued from religion. Traditional healers were believed to have been called upon by ancestors. All events in the community recognized the power of the ancestral spirits: weddings, births and deaths including even the less important ones such as getting a job (South African History Online, 2011). The only connection to God was through the ancestral spirits who were called upon by the council of elders. By demolishing the site, the colonial government hoped to weaken the Agikuyu's hope in the resistance against colonization. To this day, with the countering modernism and westernization, the place still holds sacred value and attraction to the members of the Agikuyu tribe. It serves as a cultural centre to educate the

Fig 1.012; Map showing the location of Mukurwe wa Nyagathanga. Source: Rukwaro, R, 2016

Fig 1.016; Image of the late Nobel Peace Prize laureate Wangari Maathai. Source: www.undp.org retrieved in June 2019.

Kikuyu people and visitors who are eager to understand their genesis. The centre welcomes visitors and politicians who view it as a means to mobilize the Agikuyu people towards a common cause. It also encountered a visit by the environmentalist and Nobel Peace prize laureate Wangari Maathai, Fig 1.04, who forged for the connection between the natural environment and the place in Kikuyu tradition limelight. This interest is attributed to the significance of this space in the Agikuyu tradition. It was a location for offering sacrifices to *Ngai*, which were mostly performed as a reverence to their creator or as an absolution of their sins evident through the calamities faced such as famine, epidemics, drought, internal and external conflicts (Rukwaro, 2016). In 1985, certain advancements, under the Murang'a County Council, were made to restore this spiritual place into a cultural centre that would attract the interests of curious Agikuyu people to learn of their culture as well as tourists from far and beyond. The centre would incorporate accommodation for the tourists as they learned more about the Kikuyu culture.

Plans were underway to achieve this and it would have been considered an incredible milestone in the conservation of the Kikuyu culture. Hope for other tribes in Kenya would have been uplifted too. Conarch associates architectural firm was entrusted with the responsibility of designing an upgrade of this facility with considerable attention to the culture of the people and its great importance to the tribe. The complete design consisted of a swimming pool, a classy restaurant, cottage accommodation rooms and conference rooms (Kamenju, 2012). However, the project was deemed uninspired and thus received constant rebellion from the elders of the tribe. On the contrary, the County Council did not take this resistance seriously and as a result, the elders went to court. An order to halt the construction process was commanded in 1990 when the Council had achieved 75% of the total project (Fig 1.05). Kimani, a head teacher in a

Fig 1.020; Image of the ruins left at Mukurwe wa Nyagathanga after 75% of the project was completed. Source: nation.co.ke retrieved in

Fig 1.024; Image showing the Dogon village in Mali in the 1950s. Source: Denyer S., 1978.

nearby school, claims the process came to a standstill due to the mysterious disappearance of the contractor. “We believe it was God at his mysterious best. The contractor vanished from site just when he was about to complete. And everything stalled to this day,” he claimed. (Musau,2017) The project has been neglected ever since and this unsuccessful series of events conceived the problem for this research.

1.2 Problem statement

‘The physical environment of man, especially the built environment, has not been, and still is not, controlled by the designer. This environment is the result of vernacular (or folk, or popular) architecture, and it has been largely ignored in architectural history and theory.’ (Rapoport, 1969)

It has proved to be a challenge for architects in interpreting traditional architecture caused by socio-cultural differences in the modern era (Kyalo,2009). In the primitive society, buildings were designed by its inhabitants. No architects or designers were assigned such duties. As a result, buildings defined their society in this era. The built environment was a reflection of a people’s cultural needs translated into a built form, Fig 1.06. Spaces and forms were generated unconsciously with the priority of what worked best for a society with emphasis on their traditions. Due to this revelation, the spaces and forms in a particular community were repeated until a different need arose that slightly transformed the initial design which would then encounter the same repetition and on the rhythm goes. This is solely due to the reason that traditions were shared in a certain community and since buildings were influenced by these traditions, the spaces and forms created were similar.

Step into the modern era and encounter the aspect of specialization. Architects are trained to undertake the role of designing shelter for humans. The art of creativity is gradually drilled into their minds and architecture then slowly becomes the artistic expression of its creator; the

Fig 1.028; An image of the Seagram building in New York City designed in the International Style. Source: designingbuildings.co.uk downloaded in October 2019.

architect. The architect is sheepishly bounded by architectural styles that fit into any landscape and are devoid of cultural impressions of the people in that environment. Take a case of the international style, fig 1.07, that was dominant from the 1920s and is still at play with a representation of buildings in every continent. The argument then arises with the basis of how the African people are not the same with the Asian people. Then how are their forms and spaces alike? Some may debate on the idea of architecture being a representation of its time. However, time is only representable if its preceded by a culture change that is provoked by the people. In other words, architecture is a representation of its people. The emphasis here being on its people; then in no way would two groups of people be exactly the same. They may share certain aspects but they possess distinct traditions and practices that make them different from each other. These practices and traditions define their way of living and consequently their spaces and forms. It is therefore safe to conclude that the spaces and forms of the Agikuyu and that of the Akamba may be similar but can never be identical. How do these traditions then influence the distinction in their spaces and form generation? By understanding how their spaces and forms are created will we then figure out how to attempt an interpretation of their traditional architecture in this era. Architects are urged to rethink the concept of image in restating Agikuyu traditional architecture. In an attempt to maintain a link to the past, the Agikuyu envisioned a facility in the place they consider as their origin. As earlier mentioned, the revival of the Mukurwe wa Nyagathanga was underway to design a cultural centre that would incorporate Agikuyu traditions and be a symbol of its time. However, the uninspired proposal experienced rejection from the Agikuyu elders and the construction was halted leaving an ensemble of abandoned ruins in the place considered sacred in Agikuyu culture. Conarch associates were not able to succeed in their attempts to restate

Fig. 1.032; An image of the Maasai hut, Source: nomads.org downloaded in October 2019.

Fig. 1.036; An image of Kikuyu huts at Thingira

Fig. 1.40; An image of a Kikuyu hut at the Bomas of Kenya in Nairobi, Source: upload.wikimedia.org retrieved in October 2019.

Agikuyu traditions in the 21st Century. The Agikuyu elders would have rather held their meetings under the tree than accept the comfort of a space in a classy hotel-like structure that paid no respects to their traditional culture. How then should the Agikuyu cultural centre look like? What should it incorporate to be considered acceptable to the Agikuyu people? What is the image of a Kikuyu Cultural Place? This research aims to answer these questions.

The architectural expression of the African hut is an understatement to the African traditions. Most architects are commissioned to design an African building and their concept lies in modifying the African hut. There is significantly more to the hut than its form. The African hut may seem identical to the layman, but an architect should understand that the structure, material expression as well as the space differs from community to community. This is because the culture of these communities are different and the same notion translates in what they create. The materials they use will be different since the traditions and practices as well as climatic conditions factor in the construction of their buildings. For instance, a hut in Kenya will differ from one in Namibia. A hut for the Maasai, Fig 1.8, is different from the Agikuyu hut, Fig 1.9. The problem then arises when the African hut is generalized for all African communities. There is a deeper understanding to how an Agikuyu hut came to be which is in part the reason for this research. It is just not a hut; it is a hut for the Agikuyu. This begs the question; then how did the Agikuyu hut, fig 1.10, come about?

1.3 Research questions

In light of the problems stated above, the research questions are as follows:

1. What factors determine the creation of spaces and forms?
2. How did Agikuyu practices and traditions factor in the generation of spaces and forms?

Fig. 1.44; An image showing a Kikuyu practice of grinding millet. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu retrieved in October 2019.

Fig. 1.48; An image of the Kikuyu people of Kenya during a celebration. Source: tuko.co.ke downloaded in November 2019

3. What efforts have been made to represent the Agikuyu traditional spaces and forms in the built environment today and how successful have they proven to be?

1.4 Research objectives

The following objectives were then formulated:

1. To find out the determinants that factor in space and form making.
2. To examine Agikuyu practices and traditions, fig 1.11, and their influence in the creation of spaces and forms.
3. To establish successful and failed attempts made to reinterpret traditional Agikuyu spaces and forms.

1.5 Scope and limitations

1.5.1 Scope

This study delves into understanding the vernacular representation of traditional architecture of the Agikuyu in our society today. The broad architectural spectrum is narrowed to the bounds of space and form creation. The generation of these spaces will inform on the variables to be analyzed in the findings section.

The research further limits its population study to the Agikuyu people residing in Kenya, fig. 1.12. This restriction is an endeavor to achieve maximum depth into the subject topic by narrowing the field study. Moreover, the cases to be studied are located within the boundaries of Kenya and would, therefore, be more applicable to those living in the country.

1.5.2 Limitations

The limitations encountered are as outlined below:

Fig. 1.52; A cover photo of the PhD thesis by Dr. Kamenju. Source: architecture.uonbi.ac.ke retrieved in November 2019.

Fig. 1.56; An image of a statue in Senegal built to portray African renaissance showing the infant pointing ahead to indicate the glorious future, while the woman extending her arm behind to acknowledge the troubled past. Source: slate.com downloaded in November 2019

1.5.2.1 Time

The time allocated for this study is limited to three months. This duration is not sufficient to research on a wider study area if one aims to obtain an in-depth analysis on the research topic.

1.6 Justification of the study

No study on the topic has been undertaken hence increasing its value to the literature community. On the contrary, a lot has been noted down about the Agikuyu. Previous work done on the Agikuyu tribe has encompassed their history as documented by Muriuki G. in “A history of the Kikuyu to 1904”, “Kikuyu material culture in the design of aesthetic interiors for physically challenged persons’ homes in Nyeri, Kenya” by Muriithi E. among others.

More has been written down on the Transformation of Kikuyu Traditional Architecture as in Dr. Kamenju’s PhD thesis, fig. 1.13. In his Chapter Four, he vaguely covers a sub-topic on Retrospection and Introspection where he reviews the attempts made to reinterpret the Kikuyu traditional homestead in the modern context. He covers a theoretical perspective to the literal approach to these places and their physical state in the transformation of Kikuyu Traditional Architecture. However, the thesis does not look into the layout of these spaces, organizational strategies and forms used in the traditional context that influenced the formation of these places. This research, therefore, aims to fill this gap.

1.7 Significance of the study

1.7.1 African Renaissance.

Ngugi Wa Thiong’o is a prolific writer of his time. He majors on the importance of using our traditional languages in an effort to re-spark our African flame. In the same line of thought, this study aims to revitalize African architecture in the context of the Agikuyu people. This research will offer insight on how Africans can reclaim their lost identity through their architecture, fig 1.14.

Fig. 1.60; An image of a tourist dancing with the Maasai. Source:elicitafrica.com retrieved in November 2019.

Fig. 1.64; An artistic illustration depicting the limitations written down in Chapter one. Source:clipartstation.com downloaded in November 2019

By showing how Agikuyu traditional architecture has been revived, other African communities can learn and do the same for their traditional architecture. In doing so, preservation of culture is eminent.

1.7.2 Cultural Tourism

The success of cultural tourism is banked on the idea of conserving and preserving our traditional culture. This sector thrives on the basis of the richness in culture of a specific community, i.e. the Maasai in fig. 1.15, and the uniqueness of its identity; both of which are dependent on how the architecture of a particular group is interpreted. It should display the traditional architecture of a certain era but pay respects to the modern time. This thesis will provide necessary information for architects on how it has been done, what can be done to improve the situation and consequently enrich the cultural tourism sector of our country.

1.8 Organization of study

1.8.1 Chapter one: Introduction

Chapter one breaks down the objectives of the research topic, the importance and its contribution to society. It discusses the reasons behind the study and the extent of the study. Limitations, fig. 1.16, are also penned down in this chapter. It gives an explanation on why it is important to find out how and why the Agikuyu created their spaces and forms.

1.8.2 Chapter two: Literature review

Chapter two looks into previously written works about the topic, fig. 1.17. It provides a deep understanding of the concepts of form and space making in traditional communities. It further analyzes the Agikuyu traditions and customs to understand how spaces and forms were generated. The aim of this chapter is to identify the variables of the research which will come handy in analyzing the findings.

Fig. 1.68; An image of literature books that come in handy while writing Chapter two.

Source:oxbridgeessays.com downloaded in October 2019

Fig. 1.72; An illustration of data collection and analyzing the findings in Chapter four.

Source:explorable.com retrieved in October 2019

1.8.3 Chapter three: Research methods

This chapter identifies the type of methods that the researcher will use in collecting data. The research strategy and approach are also outlined in this chapter. It also lays out the research process, types of data analysis as well as the limitations of the research methods chosen.

1.8.4 Chapter four: Findings

This chapter will explain in great detail the research findings by looking at attempts made to represent Agikuyu traditional architecture in Kenya. This entails recording as well as analyzing information, fig. 1.18, retrieved by visiting the various Agikuyu Cultural Centers in Kenya today. The effort lies in establishing whether they have been successful or failed in interpreting Agikuyu traditional architecture.

1.8.5 Chapter five: Conclusions and recommendations

After analyzing the findings, Chapter Five offers an opportunity to the researcher to put down their opinions in the conclusions section. The author will also suggest recommendations to better solve the problem of interpreting Agikuyu traditional architecture inspired from the findings explained in Chapter Four.

CHAPTER TWO:

'OUR SPACES AND FORMS,'

-THE AGIKUYU

Fig 2.01; An image of planes put together to carve out space. Source: excelsiorclasses.com retrieved in October 2019

2.1 Introduction

“The house is an institution not just a structure, created for a complex set of purposes. Because building a house is a cultural phenomenon, its form and organization are greatly influenced by the cultural milieu to which it belongs.” (Rapoport, 1969)

2.2 Form and space definition

Space is a three-dimensional boundless element where living creatures exist. It is the nothingness we see and live in. Living creatures, including human beings, crave shelter as a basic need. They wander around space to create shelter. This process is architecture. It involves creating enclosures by the deliberate use of planes as in fig 2.01. As Kahn (1957) puts it, “architecture is the thoughtful making of space”. Architecture is simply recreated by creatively defining space. This definition of space is only possible through achieving different interesting compositions by placing enclosures in form of planes to carve out bounded space from boundless space. The bounded space is the interior space of a house while the boundless space is the infinite space surrounding the house, fig 2.02. The sort of composition that covers the space in the house is the form. Form defines space and the process is what gives birth to architecture. They are the primary elements in architecture. They complement each other and are therefore inseparable (Hong Kong Institute of Architects, 2012).

Fig 2.02; An image showing the space in the house in relation to the infinite space outside. Source: pbs.twimg.com retrieved in October 2019

The character of the form then further defines the space within. Its texture, colour, height and degree of enclosure give a different quality to the space and consequently a different user experience. For example, a mashrabeya wall will give a different experience to the user as compared to a fully glassed wall. One may be brought to wonder as to why some people would prefer a completely enclosed wall to one that offers you a direct connection to nature. Aspects such as context and cultural beliefs and customs lead to this preference. This chapter will look into

Fig. 2.03; An image showing the spirit of Ubuntu,
Source: jackyyenga.com retrieved in October
2019

Fig. 2.04; An image of Archbishop Desmond
Tutu, a proponent of the Ubuntu spirit.
Source: theconversation.com retrieved in
October 2019

how cultural beliefs and customs affect how people organize their spaces and define the character of their forms.

2.3 Spatial organization and form making determinants

To discover the spatial schemata of a culture, it is important, therefore, to analyze their concepts of space.

2.31 The “Ubuntu” concept

valuating the concept of Ubuntu will form a basis in understanding and later appreciating the space-making process of the Agikuyu architecture as in fig 2.03. This sub-section expounds on the unconscious influence of the Ubuntu tradition in the formation of spaces in traditional African architecture.

Ubuntu is a Zulu term that is coined to communicate the meaning: “I am because we are.” It is a Bantu translation of humanity towards others or rather ‘the essence of being human’ (Tutu,1999) As the Zulus put it, ‘Umuntu Ngumuntu Ngabantu’ literally translated to ‘a person is a person through other persons’ (Boudreau,2012). Tutu (1999), fig 2.04, further emphasizes that a person who believes in Ubuntu exhibits a generous and unselfish personality and is consequently happy about others’ successes for he or she believes that they are part of a greater whole. It spans from the belief that humans cannot live in isolation and their existence depends on their interconnection with one another. Lundin describes Ubuntu as a philosophy that upholds the success of a group over that of an individual.

More so, a story is told of an anthropologist who was studying the customs, habits and beliefs of an African community. He decided to play a game with the children of this tribe. He had bought sweets and placed them under a tree. The game then depended on the notion that the fastest kid to get to the tree would have all the candy to himself or herself. Immediately he called out for the

Fig. 2.05; An illustration of different people coming together, Source: sheisafrica.eu retrieved in October 2019

Fig. 2.06; A plan view of a Maasai village Source: Hasey M., 2015

game to commence, the kids held each other's hands, walked towards the tree cheerfully and shared the sweets equally amongst themselves. After doing so, they all sat under the tree and munched away their presents happily. On seeing this, the anthropologist was startled. He then asked them why they had chosen to do so despite the fact that the winner could have relished at the presents on his own. In response, the kids uttered: "Ubuntu. How could any one of us be happy if all the others were sad?" (Anderson, 2012). Ubuntu flourished on its core value of 'togetherness' as illustrated in fig 2.05.

"African architecture can be looked at from different angles to achieve a full understanding. One of the perspectives that helps to achieve a good view of this architecture is the co-dependence of the African people or communities." (Chanje, 2010) Africans took care of each other, shared food together, danced and sang in unison and practiced similar beliefs and practices. Any deviation from the common social norm was illegal and punishment was due. For example, the Hehe of Tanzania had the belief that a member of the community who behaved in a different manner than his fellows would encounter death by a warlock (Denyer, 1978). This established a sense of togetherness in how they lived which consequently translated in how they built.

Take a case of the Maasai who built houses (*Enkaji*) together creating a form of enclosure as in fig. 2.06. Together they could withstand anything. The village was considered a symbol of strength in the community (Denyer,1978). They could defend each other, feed each other, share everything and as a result, they were stronger together than they were ever apart. This mentality unconsciously generated a sense of enclosure in the spatial organization of their homesteads.

2.32 Cosmic order

The cosmos is simply the universe. However, cosmos incorporates the notion of the universe as an orderly entity rather than its assumed chaotic nature. In an attempt to understand the cohesive characteristic of the universe, how different elements come together and function appropriately, the human mind has invented different theories. For example, the four elements (fire, water, air and earth) as viewed by the Eastern and North African people to represent the four cardinal points; East, West, North and South (Huffman, 2016). To further confirm this statement is the common obsession to categorize everything as male and female, including the heavenly bodies as in fig 2.07.

Fig. 2.07; An image showing the sun and the moon as male and female. Source: cropcircleconnector.com retrieved in October 2019

Fig. 2.08; A plan of a Dogon house. The dotted line illustrates the position of the man in the womb or marriage bed. Source: Denyer S., 1978.

This section is not interested in how thinkers, scientists and philosophers have contributed to this understanding. On the contrary, the researcher is more fascinated at how these speculations were strongly believed by our ancestors, in a science-less age, and how they had an effect in the creation of spatial layouts.

To illustrate this, traditional societies translated the cosmic model to a house. For instance, the Dogon people of Mali build their houses to represent a man lying inclined to his right side in the womb and in the marriage bed as in fig 2.08. One may conclude that the spatial layout is a consequence of lack of planning but little does one realize that it is a result of a complicated cosmology. The different spaces and rooms are different organs of the man's body. The villages are built in twos to represent heaven and earth in co-existence (Denyer, 1978).

2.33 Social organization

The relationship between social organization of a community and its influence on the physical space has been thoroughly reviewed. Sadoughianzadeh (2013) expounds on how space is a physical representation of a society's social organization. In other words, how people use space is

Fig. 2.09; A plan showing the village of the Bamileke people of Cameroon and how all the houses were built in reference to the chief's houses. Source: Denyer S., 1978.

Fig. 2.10; An image of the Kikuyu man's and woman's hut at Mukurwe wa Nyagathanga shrine. Source: kenyatalk.com retrieved in October 2019

influenced by how they organize themselves socially. Denyer (1978) goes on to attribute the spatial arrangement of African villages to the physical representation of the community's social structure. For example, in the Tiv community, houses were gradually built to face the new chief's house once the old chief had passed on. Some communities like the Bamileke of Cameroon arranged their houses around the chief's houses as in fig. 2.09. The chief's houses being at the top of political hierarchy then became the datum and all other houses were built in reference to it, surrounding it. This proves that the cultural behaviour patterns of a group of people are not just confined in the mental aspect but rather, expressed in their day-to-day practices (El-Aswad, 2017).

2.34 Religion

Religious beliefs played a major role in the spatial arrangement of primitive societies. Religion took the greatest consideration to the extent of gaining prominence over comfort (Rapoport, 1969). These beliefs affected the choice of their building sites and subsequently, their spaces. For example, the Lango community of Uganda never built their houses on hills as the natural feature was associated with housing Jok, the spirit. Any close proximity to Jok was considered to be dangerous (Denyer, 1978).

2.35 Gender

The strong relationship between gender as a social construct and space as a physical construct is obviously anticipated as social life takes place in and through space (Sadoughianzadeh, 2013). In most African communities, the position of men and women had completely different standings in the day-to-day social life of the community. Take a case of the Agikuyu people in the olden days who had specific huts for the husband and another one for each wife he married. The wives and husbands lived separately and only stayed in the same hut during conjugal visits. The form and

Fig. 2.11; An image of the Birom village entrance designed for defense purposes. Source: Denyer S.,1978.

Fig 2.12; A plan image of the Birom village showing the strategic position of the beer store. Source: Denyer S.,1978.

spatial layouts of the huts, fig 2.10, were different as the duties of each gender were clearly distinct.

2.36 Security

In the traditional setting, each community having achieved a great economic status was always at risk from her neighbours who wanted what she had. It was an equivalent to 'power is taken and not given' especially for the communities whose leaders did not believe in the solemn art of trading and negotiating. For this reason, certain communities such as the *Birom* of Northern Nigeria created a narrow tunnel-like entrance of euphorbia hedge as in fig 2.11 almost 4.5metres high and one kilometre away from their houses to frustrate the Hausa northmen raiders. The tunnel was designed like a maze to further confuse the Northmen as the branches either led to the blind alleys or back to the main tunnel (Denyer,1978). This fortification is almost similar to the one used by the Agikuyu in defense of their Maasai neighbours as will be later seen in this chapter.

2.37 Way of gaining a livelihood

It is not a shock that all communities would protect whatever simply feeds them with the utmost care. It ensures their survival in the universe. For this reason, some communities would first build the hut that sheltered their source of livelihood and the rest of the houses would follow surrounding this particular hut and consequently protecting it. With all the eyes of the residents of that homestead on this particular hut, then there was no need of a video surveillance. Take a case of the Birom of Northern Nigeria who first erected a beer store as in fig 2.12 before the other huts proving how important it was to their survival.

Fig. 2.13; An image of Chief Njiri, his wives, his children and his VW Beetle in his *mucii* in the 1960s. Source: [pinterest.com](https://www.pinterest.com) retrieved in October 2019.

Fig. 2.14; A plan of the *mucii*. Source: mukuyu.wordpress.com retrieved in October 2019.

2.4 Agikuyu way of life influencing formation of spaces and forms

The *genre de vie* is a term used by Max Sorre to define the cultural, social and spiritual aspects that influence and affect form. In short, houses and settlements built constitute the *genre de vie* of a particular community (Rapoport, 1969).

According to Rapoport (1969), some of the important facets of the *genre de vie* that affect built form are:

- Family structure
- Some basic needs.
- Position of women.
- Privacy.
- Social interaction.

In order to understand how forms and spaces are influenced by the *genre de vie*, the next section explains the traditional Agikuyu set-up vis a vis the aspects mentioned above to understand how these factors affected the formation of their spaces and forms and most importantly, what spaces and forms were created in the process.

2.41 Family structure

As per the original myth of the Agikuyu, the society was considered matriarchal. In the 19th Century, however, the social and political organization was patrilineal. The community embraced polygamy and the man being the head of the family, lived with his many wives, children and cattle together. They were all his property and were named after him. Since the head of the family had to take care of all he owned, he then created his own *mucii*, the homestead, fig 2.13 to house all his belongings.

Fig. 2.15; An image showing the congestion of the *mucii* of a wealthy man with many wives. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu retrieved in October 2019.

Fig. 2.16; An illustration of the family structure

Fig. 2.17; A sketch of a village showing the widow's house on the right without a spike at the top. Source: Kamenju, J., 2012

2.411 The *mucii*, homestead

Every space in the *mucii* had a purpose. Every purpose was a response to social, economic and political needs of the Agikuyu basic unit.

The man had his own hut, the *thingira*. Being the head of the family, serious matters affecting the *mucii* were first discussed here before informing the female members. It was the *mucii's* parliament (Anyamba, 1994). It is also where the man ate, slept and received guests (Maathai, 2006). And therefore, with these functions and for defence purposes, it only makes sense for the *thingira* to be located close to the entrance of the courtyard; which is exactly where the Agikuyu situated it as in fig 2.14.

The family residing in the *mucii* was the *nyumba*. The *nyumba* was the 'core of the Kikuyu society' (Muriuki, 1969). It belonged to the patriarch of the family. The people residing in that *mucii* were identified as his. It was his realm. And he therefore housed all his people and belongings; the wives, the children, the granaries. The spatial arrangement of the *mucii* clearly illustrates the distribution of the houses from the man's house, his wives and children's children in a hierarchical format. It is a clear indication of how the social organization of the Agikuyu has affected the spatial layout of the *mucii*.

The man and his wives' houses are at the periphery of the main courtyard. The sons develop their own semi-autonomous courtyards in relation to their father's courtyard adjacent to their mother's house (*nyumba*). Their houses are situated at the edge of their courtyards. The grandsons do the same on their father's courtyards and gradually the *mucii* increases in size. If at all the compound becomes overcrowded, one of the sons or grandsons could move to a neighbouring compound and the cycle would start again (Anyamba, 1993). Some men had ten wives or more and the

Fig. 2.18; A sketch showing the houses surrounding a middle space, the *nja*. Source: mukuyu.wordpress.com retrieved in October 2019

Fig. 2.19; An image showing the character of the *nja*, that of bare earth, swept clean in today's homestead at Karukis in Murang'a neighbouring the Mukurwe wa Nyagathanga. Source: mukuyu.wordpress.com retrieved in October 2019

mucii could be mistaken for a village as in fig 2.15. The different *nyumbas* that share the same male ancestor belong to the same *mbari* as in fig 2.16.

Kikuyu customs greatly translated in the spatial arrangement and form of the *mucii*. For instance, the first wife's house was the one directly opposite the entrance. Each wife had her own *nyumba* (house), whose access was from the *nja* (courtyard). The widow's house, man's mother, also lives in the *mucii*. Her *nyumba* can be differentiated from the others in two ways. The first is, her spike has been removed as illustrated in fig 2.17 to symbolize the loss of her husband. The other reason is her door does not face the *nja* but rather, a smaller courtyard has been created for her privacy and the door thus opens to it. Her access, however, is from the *nja*. Needless to say, this would not have been the case were her husband still alive (Kamenju,2012).

At this juncture, it is imperative that we look into the spaces created in the *mucii* and the functions they served. They are outlined as follows:

2.4111 *Nja*, the courtyard

This was an open space in the middle of the *mucii* as in fig 2.14. All the houses in the *mucii* were referenced in relation to this space as in fig 2.18. Its view was one of a bare earth as no grass could survive the constant movement of people, goats and playing children. According to Routledge (1910), the *nja* was always kept clean, swept every day and on other occasions, more than once. This custom has been retained until now as one can see in fig 2.19 in a homestead in Murang'a. This was to ensure dangerous animals such as snakes could be clearly noticed. Moreover, cleaning the *nja* was to ensure no man or woman tripped and fell in this space as this was considered a taboo and purification would then be underway.

At times, the pumpkin plant crept its way into the *nja* and a small hedge would be used to support its growth. This hedge would form an enclosure that would be used for other activities

Fig. 2.20; An image showing the drying of coffee beans in today's homestead at Karukis in Murang'a neighbouring the Mukurwe wa Nyagathanga. Source: image.slidesharecdn.com retrieved in October 2019

such as external cooking. Drying of millet and other farm produce was and still is, fig 2.20, done in the *nja*. In addition to this, preparation of food such as the grinding of grains using the pestle and mortar as well as the grinding stone were activities done in this space. All these activities befitted the woman and this space was her realm. (Kamenju, 2012)

2.41112 *Thome*

This was the entrance pathway into the *mucii*. Its position always depended on the customs the family followed. Some had it facing the east, others directed it towards the west while the rest positioned it facing the sacred mountains like Mt. Kenya. (Leakey, 2007)

2.41113 *Boi-ini*

This space was where the man entertained his guests. It was positioned close to the entrance just next to his thingira as in fig 2.14. The male guests hardly roamed around in the *nja*. (Kamenju,2012)

Fig 2.21; A plan showing a mucii layout. Source: Anyamba,1994

Fig. 2.22; A sketch of the nyumba. Source: Anyamba, 1994.

Fig. 2.23; A plan of the traditional nyumba. Source: pinterest.com retrieved in October 2019

2.42 Some basic needs

According to Rapoport (1969), a community defined itself not on the basis of whether their houses had doors or windows but rather cultural influence was due on where they placed their openings, the orientation and the form. Therefore, certain needs had to be met. Each community, however, responded to satisfying their needs in how they understood it better. In other words, how their cultural beliefs and customs propelled them to. It was never a matter of whether one cooks or eats, since this was bound to happen for their survival, but how and where they do so. Here are some of the forms and spaces that came about to meet some of the Agikuyu's basic needs:

2.421 The nyumba

It was the main house in the mucii. Most scholars have researched about the nyumba, fig 2.22, and certain elements such its spatial organization has proved to be consistent in all the cases. Its internal diameter ranges between 15 to 20 feet (Leakey,2007). The spaces in the nyumba were created to house the common basic needs of food, shelter and clothing. With reference to fig. 2.23, they are as follows:

Entrance porch, githaku

This was a defined space just outside the woman's nyumba that housed activities such as external cooking and the entertaining of her guests. Most people categorize the space as the entry porch covered by an overhang of thatched grass. This space was mainly used for storage purposes as it housed the pestle and mortar, the firewood, the grinding stones, the broken pot, cooking utensils and large fireplace stones. The supports for the overhang were only on the front part.

Fig. 2.24; An image showing the ruri at Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's house in Limuru. Source: Author, September 2019

Doorway, *muromo*

The access was directly connected to the *nja*. It was about 2 feet wide with a location that took into consideration the direction of the prevailing wind. Never would the *muromo* face the incoming wind. There were two posts marking the doorway and were always placed before the other posts while constructing the *nyumba*.

Lobby, *ruri*

This was a transitional space, fig 2.24, where the woman could offload her basket before entering the *nyumba*. The *ruri* divided the entry in two ways; to the left was the access used by the goats while to the right was used by humans. The people were not allowed to use the goats' entrance. The far left was the *gaturwa-ini*, a storage space for the farming tools while to the far right was the *ndigithu*, a pot for storing water.

Firewood stack, *muhando*

This stack of wood was right behind the *ruri*. The girl's bed space was the closest to the stack as her duty was to ensure there was always firewood in the *nyumba*. If the supply ran low, she was to gather more firewood to replenish the stock.

Firewood rack, *itara*

The firewood rack was placed above ground level such that the heat from the fire below could facilitate the drying of the firewood whilst ensuring it does not burn. This firewood was rarely used and was reserved for the wet season to accompany the wet wood in producing fire. The rack was also essential in preventing sparks from reaching the grass-thatched roof. The rack was supported by two beams spanning through the elevated square as in fig. 2.23.

The kitchen and the hearth, *riko*

Riko was the square space defined by the four columns that supported the roof. It also referred to the fireplace strategically located at the centre of the *nyumba*. The fireplace, fig 2.25, was made

Fig. 2.25; A photograph of the fireplace at Riuki Cultural Centre in Kiambu. Source: Author, September 2019

up of three stones, two big ones and a small one, firmly fixed in the ground by digging them in (Leakey,2007).

This space was imperative in strengthening the family's unity as they would all gather around the fireplace in the evenings. The woman would sit on the opposite side of the right entrance on a low four-legged stool. The man's seating space was close to the goats'. He would come in last. The children fashioned themselves comfortably on the floor while the older girls sat in their kiriri. Only the girl helping the mother cook would be positioned close to the riko. Stories were told and riddles, *ndai*, were invented and solved around this fireplace. Little did they realize they were learning and sharpening their minds in the process.

The kitchen sides, *mihirito* (Singular-Mwihirito)

Mwihirito represents the spaces at the periphery of the squared riko. It simply means 'side'. The sitting arrangement was influenced by the riko. It was the datum. The woman's side was the 'tongue clicking side', *itheng'ukiro*. This is because she expressed her anger with the click of her tongue. The displeasure would have been directed towards the husband who was not able to reach her as it was prohibited for him to cross over the fireplace. Moreover, the children seated by her side would be constantly irritating her. Through this ordeal, the girls on the right would be laughing hence their space would be named *mitheko*, the laughter side. The side neighbouring the goats' space (*kweru*) was called *mwihirito wa kweru*. This space was allocated to the boys and children. The space close to the door, *mwihirito wa muromo*, was left for the man and the visitors.

The goats' space (the white place), *kweru*

To the left was where the goats lay. It was also the space where young uncircumcised boys, who were old enough to not sleep with their mother, slept. The reason behind its name, *kweru*, was

probably due to the fact that it was always kept tidy to expel the goats' droppings and ashes poured to dry and remove the smell. The ashes spread left a white colour on the floor thus the space acquired its name, the white place. Consciously or unconsciously, the presence of the goats in the nyumba proved advantageous as the alkali in their urine dismissed the presence of fleas or jiggers. Poorer families that could not afford goats hence suffered from the infestation of the mentioned blood-sucking insects.

The food store, gatari

Between the white place and the woman's sleeping space was the space where spare stools, cooked food and bags were kept. More importantly, the space between the gatari and the kweru was where the woman gave birth. Assisted by a midwife and other women, the woman lying on a cow's hide would then deliver.

Woman's sleeping space, uriri

This space was at the farthest end directly opposite the entrance. Its dimensions were approximately six feet long and four feet wide. It was enclosed with a planks partition. The bed was raised at about 18 inches above ground level. It was made in a sloping manner with the head side at a higher position than the legs section. The head space was adjacent to the store to the right, thegi. On the sides of the bed were where the woman hanged her jewellery worn during the dances and important ceremonies.

The woman's store, thegi

On the far right corner was a storage space privately used by the woman. Only her grown daughters could enter this space. It was only right as it kept her most treasured items; honey, cooking utensils, fat, fermented milk and pots. Other commodities were hidden in bags hanged on the wall such as in fig. 2.27.

Fig. 2.27; An image showing the storage of commodities in bags hanged on the wall.
Source: Leakey L., 2007

Fig. 2.80; Photograph of the traditional bed made using banana leaves at Riuki Cultural Centre in Kiambu. Source: Author, September 2019

The girls' sleeping space, kiriri

Young unmarried daughters would rest in this space. The bed, fig. 2.28, was constructed in the same manner as their mother's. The higher side was adjacent to the ram's pen as their legs faced the woman's store, thegi. Their partition was plastered with a mixture of mud and cow dung.

The ram-fattening space, gicegu

Every house had its share of goats (Leakey, 2007). The ram was tended to by the woman while the he-goat stayed with the man in his thingira. The floor of this space was raised with sticks arranged closely together in a calculated fashion leaving small spaces to let the rams' droppings through. The pen never had an entrance as the ram never left. Food was brought to it by the woman. The aim was to fatten it to feed the people in a ceremony. When let out in the nja, the visitors would admire it. Praise was given to the woman with the fattest ram. It would be considered proof of her hardwork. The fat acquired from the ram would be hers. It was regarded precious as it would later soften clothes made of leather, mixed with honey to offer delicious treats and used in the preparation of tobacco.

2.422 The thingira

This is the man's hut; his private space. Unlike the nyumba, it was much smaller in size maybe due to accommodating much lesser activities. Kamenju (2012) estimates its diameter to be around 12-15 feet. It further differed from the nyumba as it lacked internal partitions.

The reason as to why a man owned a *thingira* has barely been documented. However, certain scholars believe that since it was prohibited for the man to enter the nyumba before the animals and children did, then this space was created in an effort to kill time as the necessary activities preceded. Such activities also incorporated the cooking of food.

Fig. 2.88; A plan of the thingira. Source: Author, 2019

Doorway, muromo

There exists one entry and exit. It is connected to the external courtyard, *nja*, though not directly. However, young uncircumcised boys' or unmarried men's thingiras would never open into the courtyard. They would be positioned close to the gate.

Goats' space, kwa mburi

As earlier mentioned, every hut had its own share of goats. To the left was a space assigned to the shelter of goats.

Rack, Rutara

Gicegu, Goat Fattening Pen

Just like the *nyumba's* ram-fattening pen, the *thingira* also housed the fattening of the goat.

Firewood, Ngu

This space was where the firewood used to feed onto the fire was placed.

The Bed, Uriri

To the right was the man's bed in form of a raised platform. It was constructed in the same way the woman's bed was. However, it lacked any form of screening.

At times, when the kids were grown up and the conjugal visits could not be housed by the *nyumba*, the wife/wives would instead visit the man in his thingira.

Front Overhang, Githaku

In this space, the man sits on a stool beside his walking stick and watches the activities of his mucii while sheltered from the scorching sun. If at one point he decides to enter his thingira, for any reason whatsoever, then he leaves the walking stick and his stool outside. This was a common indication that the head of the house was around. However, if he left the compound, there would be no sign of his walking stick or even his stool.

Fig. 2.89; An image of a Kikuyu hut. Source: Routledge, 1910.

Fig. 2.97; A drawing showing the different holes made for the construction of the hut. Source: Routledge, 1910.

a, a, a- wall posts

b, b, b, b- posts to support the eaves

c, c, c, c - central pillar to carry the weight of the roof

-----indicates the ties from wall plate to wall plate.

2.423 The form of the hut

Every Kikuyu hut, fig. 2.30, whether large or small was constructed in the same way. According to Routledge (1910), the following procedure was followed:

Clearing and marking out the site

The men cleared out the site enough for the portion of the land that is viable for construction. A circular marking of about 15 feet to 20 feet, fig. 2.31, would be done. No tape measure was used. The guide depended on the natural eye.

Digging the inner holes

Nineteen holes equidistant from one another are dug on the marked line. The hole was made by stabbing the digging knife into the ground or a pointed stick and retracting it using the hands. It is dug to the size of a man's arm while the surrounding soil is left undisturbed.

Fixing the inner posts

Into each of the nineteen holes, posts as wide as the size of the wrist and up to 4 feet in height above the ground level. They are bifurcated at the upper end.

Fixing the interior pillars

These are the pillars that support and carry the weight of the roof. An oblong shape is marked equidistant from the centre of the circle as in fig. 2.32. Posts five feet in height are placed at the corners of this figure. They are bifurcated at the ends.

Kamba, the material

A shrub that goes by the name *Kamba* is used in the place of strings and rope.

Preparing the roof frame

A strong hoop that has a diameter of 3 feet is bound together using rods till it forms a thickness that equates that of a wrist. This hoop is then laid on the ground. At the centre of the hoop, a 4 feet high stake sharpened at both ends is driven into the ground, as in fig. 2.33. The smaller ends

Fig. 2.105; A drawing of the roof framework.
Source: Routledge, 1910.

a, a- The axial stake.

b, b- Rods that are tied to ends of rafters,

c¹- Main hoop on which the frame is built.

c²- Supplementary hoop to give rigidity.

Fig. 2.113; An image of nyumba ya rutwago.
Source: oldeastafricapostcards.com
downloaded in October 2019

of similar-sized rods are then positioned and tied at the midpoint of the axial stake. Each rod is then forced to the ground and a convex curve of the rod directed downwards is achieved. After it curves, each rod is fastened onto the hoop. For firmness, another hoop may be added to ensure the roof frame is stronger. The axial stake is seen to protrude out of the apex as a *mucoke* (spike), a major characteristic of Agikuyu huts. The result is a conical shaped roof with flares at the edges and a spike at the top as in fig. 2.32.

The wall plate

On the Y-shaped ends of the nineteen posts are laid bent rods that are interwoven together to form an external hoop that further increases the strength of the roof framework. This ring supports the sticks that carry the weight of the thatch.

The walls

There existed three different types of wall constructions and this consequently reflected on the names accorded to each one. *Nyumba ya rutwago* was a hut that was made using a brushwood wall as in fig 2.33, *nyumba ya mihirigo* was one made using a hewn planks construction as in fig. 2.34 and *nyumba ya ndoro* was one made of poles and wickerwork lattice and young saplings and then finished with mud (Kamenju, 2012). The construction of the hewn planks wall was an expensive affair and only seen in the case of a 'wealthy man in a forest district'. (Routledge, 1910)

The rafters and the apex

The Kikuyu huts had a total of eight rafters, *miratho*, and two hoops, *mbara* just below the rafters as in fig. 2.35. These rafters in the form of young samplings of the *muyuyu* (*Chaetacme aristata*), *muhethu* (*Treama orientalis*) or *mutundu* (*Neoboutania macrocalyx*) were tied onto the wall plate with strips of bark. (Kamenju, 2012). The rafters project 4feet beyond the wall plate to form the eaves. The other ends are brought together to form a 40 degrees pitched roof. The framework

Fig. 2.121; An image of nyumba ya mihirigo at the Bomas of Kenya built using the hewn planks wall. Source: jambonairobi.co.ke downloaded in August 2019.

Fig. 2.129; A drawing of the rafters. Source: Kamenju J., 2012

Fig. 2.137; An image of the *ruthiru*, bracken fern. Source: wildadironacks.org downloaded in November 2019

earlier constructed is then adjusted to this pitch and the rafters fastened (Routledge, 1910). The rods used to make the rafters were thin, about 35-75mm in diameter. They would have been unable to support the 3-5 women who would later climb onto it to do the thatching of the roof. The strength of the structure was improved by the internal twin columns at each corner of a perfect square and evenly spaced columns on the sides of the square. The columns on each side of the square were evenly spaced. However, the rafter fell right at the centre of the sides of the square. A flying arched rafter from one corner of the square to the next, the *muikio*, was therefore built to support these columns (Kamenju, 2012).

Provision for the thatch attachment

Flexible rods are now woven and tied around the rafters to form hoops and horizontal bands just above the primary and secondary rafters that ties the rafters together in the form of a wooden rope as in fig. 2.37. The interval between the horizontal bands depended on the length of the thatching material and in most cases it was approximately 18 inches.

Provision for the eaves support

The rafters having been projected 4 feet beyond the wall plate form a deep eave whose butts have been tied together and connected using flexible rods. At the extreme ends of these rafters, on the ground, are dug holes of intervals of 4 feet and post fixed and secured firmly using earth material (Routledge, 1910). These posts carry the load of the eaves. However, they are only positioned in front of the nyumba and form the *githaku*, the front porch.

Roof thatching

The thatching was always done by women after the men have created the necessary framework. The *ruthiru*, bracken fern, fig. 2.36, or banana leaves were first laid down to attain a firm impenetrable bed to place the grass, reeds or flags. Bundles of long grass, the most popular being

Fig. 2.145; An image showing the rafters tied with hoops in preparation for thatch attachment. Source: [pinterest.com](https://www.pinterest.com) retrieved in November 2019

Fig. 2.153; An image of young Kikuyu girls carrying firewood in the traditional society. Source: [Il Popolo Kikuyu](https://www.illpopolo.com) retrieved in October 2019

nyaragita, or reeds, *ithanji*, were then gathered and tied at their butts using *kamba* on the lowest hoop or bands that is connected to the rafters. A circular formation of the tied grass is then achieved and this is constantly repeated starting from the lower part of the roof to the apex on the different bands until the hut is fully thatched. The roof is then finished by tying the top bundles of the grass into a spike, the *mucobe*.

2.43 Position of women

“The stranger passing through the land who sees the women working with bent backs in the fields, or toiling along the road with huge loads of firewood, obtains little idea of the home life of a Kikuyu woman, and that little is erroneous,” (Routledge, 1910)

The life of the woman in the old Agikuyu society involved a lot of responsibility from childhood. As a girl, she worked in the fields, learnt how to make baskets, assisted her mother with cooking, walked miles and miles to look for firewood and made sure that this essential material was in abundance for the sake of the rainy season, fig. 2.38. As she grew, more duties were bestowed upon her in addition to the ones she was already responsible for. She gets married. Nature detects that she gives birth to as many children as possible. The more the merrier and even better if her offspring would include the male child. This is because the male child was to assist with the male duties such as herding the goats. If the wife did not give birth to a baby boy, then the husband would have to take care of herding the goats till his old age came calling. In return, the woman’s work was to till the land and tend to it until it provides food for her family. The woman was essentially the homemaker, the man protected the family. (Routledge, 1910)

The piece of land which the woman tends to is considered hers. She takes pride in it especially if its larger than her neighbours even though it entails more work. It is then expected that after harvesting this large produce, she will need to store it for her family which will come in handy

Fig. 2.161; An image of a granary at the Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, photo taken in September 2019

during the drought period. The granary was her space. She could not share it even with the members of the same homestead she was in. Her position in the community then gave rise to this important space and form, the granary.

The granary, ikumbi

Every wife owned at least one granary. Some owned more than one. The first wife's granaries (*nyakiambi*) were built at the sides of the courtyard's entry. The other wives' granaries were built next to their houses on either side of the entrances to the new courtyards, extended to accommodate their sons just behind their *nyumbas*.

The granaries were used for storing grains; maize, beans and millet. They were important in the preservation of the harvests as they prevented attack by moisture that would consequently cause the grains to rot. For this reason, the granaries were raised 18 inches off the ground on a square platform made of sticks and stones as shown in fig. 2.39. They were also useful in keeping old pots, gourds, bags and other unnecessary things.

The construction of the granaries was in three parts. It comprised the making of the base platform as in fig. 2.40, the granary container as in fig. 2.41 and finally, the thatching as in fig. 2.42.

Fig. 2.185; A drawing showing the construction plan of the granary base stand. Source: Kamenju J., 2012

Fig. 2.177; An image of women weaving the granary container. Source: Kamenju J., 2012

Fig. 2.169; An image of a person thatching the granary. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu retrieved in October 2019

Fig. 2.193; A drawing showing the Agikuyu land and their neighbours. Source:

Fig. 2.201; An image of the traditional homestead entry lined with banana groves. Source: Kamenju J., 2012.

2.44 Privacy

“Each homestead has its own little enclosure, and in old days each was invariably surrounded by a high green hedge or stockade, which was entered by an arch of greenery usually so low as to necessitate stooping; this served as an enclosure for the cattle, for defense, and for purposes of concealment.” (Routledge, 1910)

As earlier stated in this chapter, the art of defense is a major factor in determining the making of spaces and forms. Communities have to protect themselves and their belongings from their neighbours. To do so means creating barriers and forms of fortifications which the community perceives to be most effective in their protection. The Agikuyu were not any different. The Maasai neighbored the Agikuyu to the North and South as in fig. 2.43. They shared a ‘love-hate relationship’ (Kamenju, 2012). They traded together, intermarried, shared certain customs and also raided each other. To ensure their safety and privacy from these Nilotes, the Agikuyu fenced their homesteads with a high green hedge and a concealed entry so low people would bend to access it. Some homesteads went on to have two fences; an outer one and an inner one. Just like the Birom in fig. 2.11, some entrances were lined with banana plantations forming a grove-like tunnel where the visitor coming could be anticipated from a far as in fig. 2.44. The concept of defense further affected the form of the homestead. For instance, the homesteads of the Agikuyu living closest to the Maasai like those in South Kabete differed than of the ones staying in Murang’a. This is because the homesteads of those living in the former was larger as the married sons created their own courtyards out of their father’s main courtyard and lived together in the same homestead as a response to their need of security. Residing together meant that in large numbers they could have a better chance of defeating their neighbours in a war raid as compared to the father and each of his sons living on their own as it was in other districts. The

Fig. 2.209; An image of a court proceeding in session. Source: Routledge, 1910

Fig. 2.217; A drawing showing the spatial organization of a court proceeding held in a homestead. Source: Anyamba T., 1993

- 1- Ikumbi, the granaries
- 2- Ita, the warriors
- 3- Atumwo, errand boys
- 4- Nyumbas and thingira
- 5- Muranja, lesser judges
- 6- Kiama, judges
- 7- Njama, elders

father would have been easy prey to the raiders especially if his old age seemed to incapacitate him.

2.45 Social interaction

Man is a social animal. This was even more so in the older society. The 'Ubuntu' phenomenon was the daily norm. The Agikuyu lived in homesteads; homesteads that were grouped into villages of families and families that shared the same ancestry to the same clan, *mbari*. All these people socially interacted in one way or the other; through parties, songs and dances, initiation and even trading. It is more of an interest in 'how' and 'where' (Rapoport, 1969) the Agikuyu people met that concerns this thesis. In other words, how and where they made these spaces, the character and forms.

Court proceedings

These were held in order to reach a verdict on a problem concerning the community. Lengthy debates were common in a court session as the Agikuyu have a way with words. A *shauri* or discussion is held in an open space. The parties meant to be heard participate while the spectators look on as in fig. 2.45. Order was maintained with the passing of the *njuguma*, a wooden ornamental stick passed from one speaker to another. This ensured no two people could speak at the same time (Routledge, 1910).

The Agikuyu judicial system was composed of five groups namely; the elders (*njama*), the warriors (*ita*), the judges (*kiama*), the lesser judges (*muranja*) and the errand boys (*atumwo*). These different groups would hardly ever be in the same court session as each group engaged in different administrative duties. For instance, the *muranja* were concerned with civil and religious duties only, the *kiama* engaged in civil cases such as murder, seduction, wounding, theft and religious duties while the *njama* were responsible for civil and religious duties. The *muranja* were never

Fig. 2.225; An image showing the art of storytelling in progress. Source: pinterest.com downloaded in June 2019.

Fig. 2.233; An image of a *guuka* telling stories to his grandchildren. Source: pinterest.com retrieved in July 2019.

allowed to speak in a civil case involving theft and would just listen (Routledge, 1910). They were composed of young married men. In a case where all the different groups would take place in a court case held in a homestead, the spatial organization would be as in fig. 2.46. The arrangement was always held in a circle with the spectators on the outer side of the circle but maintaining the purity of this shape.

Cultural education

“The cultural and historical traditions of the Gikuyu people have been verbally handed down from generation to generation” (Kenyatta, 1965). Unlike the western system, cultural education was an unconscious self-involving practical process that was done over a long period of time in different stages. There was no special school. The homestead was the school. For instance, learning in this era was through oral means such as storytelling, fig. 2.47, dance and music, folktales, riddles, games and other puzzles. Other practical ways to test the power of observation and memory of a boy was mixing the herds of cows of different estates and asking the young boy to distinguish those that are from his family (Kenyatta, 1965). In other words, participants learnt without knowing, ‘knowing not that they knew’. (Mukuyu)

Storytelling

Fig. 2.48 shows a *guuka*, Gikuyu grandfather, telling stories and fairytales to the children surrounding him. The children are happily enjoying the stories while cozying up around each other. Little do they know that this unconscious effort by their grandfather is a History class in progress. The children freely sit around him, play with his clothes, white hair and beard, lie on each other and in the most primitive of ways, make up space.

The mother plays a major role in educating her children. While preparing food in the evenings, she would tell them stories as in fig. 2.49. The children would be involved in saying riddles and

Fig. 2.241; A picture of a Gikuyu mother telling stories to her children while preparing food. Source: Kenyatta J., 1965.

Fig. 2.249; An image of older women engaged in a dance, *mugoiyo*. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu retrieved in August 2019.

amusing each other about certain tribal legends while the mother listens and contributes to the tales. She would also teach them about the laws and customs, especially the moral code and rules of etiquette, of the community (Kenyatta, 1965).

Games

The children are allowed to freely play with each other and the parents not allowed to have a say in what they could indulge in as long as it is not a danger to their health. Games allow children to practice what they see at home and imitate their elders. For example, they play a game of husband and wives, and build models of houses and cattle sheds with what they can easily find. The girls play the roles of the wives while the boys play the husbands' role. This is in line with what they have witnessed in their homesteads which explains why the homestead is the school as Kenyatta (1965) states. The little girls try to make little baskets and grind corn as well as make little pots with clay and pretend to cook imaginary food.

Song and dance

Till today, the Agikuyu people greatly appreciate the art of music. Traditionally, they would sing in almost all occasions even while constructing a hut. It was a common characteristic of the Agikuyu to sing inspiring songs while performing certain tasks as it was stated 'to work in a happy mood is to make the task easier, and to relieve the heart from fatigue.' ("*Koruta wera na ngoro theru ni kohothia wera na konyihia minoga*" (Kenyatta,1965).

Dances would accompany the music. Dancing was even more important as it was considered a process which members of the community could find their soulmates (Leonard,2011). It was also a means for the people to let loose and be free with each other after days of hardwork and toil to fend for their livelihood. This was mainly practiced during the months of January and February

Fig. 2.257; An image of the *gichukia* dance. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu retrieved in August 2019

Fig. 2.265; An illustration of a woman and man dancing in the *gichukia* dance. Source: Kamenju J., 2002.

after the annual harvests when the weather was cool and dry (Kamenju,2012). As Thiong'o (1965) puts it in an attempt to describe the aura during a circumcision ceremony;

“Everyone went into a frenzy of excitement. Old and young, women and children, all were there losing themselves in the magic motion of the dance. Men shrieked and shouted and jumped into the air as they went round in a circle ... Women, stripped to the waist, with their thin breasts flapping on their chests, went round and round the big fire, swinging their hips and contorting their bodies in all sorts of provocative ways, but always keeping the rhythm. They were free. Age and youth had become reconciled for this one night. And you could sing about anything and talk of the hidden parts of men and women without feeling that you had violated the otherwise strong social code that governed people's relationships, especially the relationship between young and old, man and woman.”

The dances were performed at dusk. The participants proudly dressed up for the event. Those who did not have the expected attire would feel ashamed at the dance (Ndegwa, 1992). And they then headed to the destination, mostly around the *Mukuyu* tree. Dancers were organized according to age and gender. For instance, the young girls engaged in *ihindi rimwe*, a ‘one-bone’ dance; the older men, *mugoiyo*, fig. 2.50, young women and men *kibata* and *gichukia* while the older women were involved in the *ndumo* and *gitiro* dances. The uncircumcised young boys had their *nguru*. (Kamenju,2012)

The different types of dances displayed a highly elaborated concept of spatial organization. For the purposes of attaining depth, the study will review the *gichukia* dance to understand the space-making process of this dance.

Gichukia

This dance, fig. 2.51, was performed by the initiated girls and the Agikuyu warriors around the *Mukuyu* tree. The couples form circular rings around the *Mukuyu* tree. The man and the woman stand close together facing each other. The men stand upright with their arms placed stiffly on the

Fig. 2.269; An image of a woman transporting her goods using the kiondo. Source: flickr.com retrieved in November 2019.

Fig. 2.273; An illustration showing the relationship of the kiondo construction and the gichukia dance to the cosmic theory. Source: Kamenju J., 2002.

woman's neck pointing towards the centre of the circle. The women encircle their arms around the man's waist as in fig. 2.52 (Kamenju,2002). The spatial arrangement of this dance is as a result of the Kikuyu cosmology. Earlier in this chapter, the author explained how the need for cosmic order determined the creation of spaces and forms. This cosmology is better explained in the making of the *kiondo* in the material culture section of this chapter as written below.

2.5 Material culture

It is important to understand what led to the creation of the Agikuyu spaces and forms. It is even more imperative to unravel the character of these spaces. What they were made up of; especially if the creation of these little forms were influenced by a greater theory. This section will look into the *kiondo* and the Gikuyu stool as they were the two materials that contributed to the uniqueness of the Agikuyu formation of spaces. This means that unlike the pots and gourds that were also found in other communities, the *kiondo* and the Gikuyu stool were highly distinct.

The *Kiondo*

In a simple definition, the *kiondo* is a container made by the Gikuyu woman to assist her in carrying foodstuffs to and fro places such as the market as in fig. 2.53. In a deeper definition, the *kiondo* is a complex material symbolizing the spiral of life. Its construction starts at a navel (*mukonyo*) and the Gikuyu woman weaves around it to create different sizes and types of the *kiondo*. All these spiral layers are connected representing the human being's connection to the web of life. The *kiondo*'s construction is a marriage between the upright warps, *mirugamo*, being held by the horizontal weft, *rurigi*, explaining how the man and the woman held each other in the *gichukia* dance as illustrated in fig. 2.54 (Kamenju, 2002). In the same way the dancers move sensuously around the tree (navel), the Gikuyu woman weaves together the *mirugamo* and *rurigi* strings around the navel to infinity.

Fig. 2.275; A photograph of *iturwa* at Mukurwe wa Nyagathanga. Source: beadsafariscollection.co.ke retrieved in November 2019

Fig. 2.277; An image of the modern Gikuyu stool with decorations. Source: izi.travel downloaded in November 2019

The Gikuyu stool

The traditional Gikuyu stool was known as *giturwa* (plural- *iturwa*). It was made by a professional wood carver known as *mwai wa iti* who created the stools from the *muringa*, *mununga*, *mukuyu*, *muhuti*, *mururi*, *muthaiti* and the *mukui* trees. It was characterized by a depressed centre for the bum. There was a clear distinction between the *giturua*, the woman's four-legged stool that was used in the kitchen and the *njung'ua*, the man's three or four-legged stool that was smaller in size and easy to carry around.

The traditional stools, fig. 2.55, were never decorated unlike their modern interpretation as in fig. 2.56. They were only finished with a brush of castor oil and left to attain a mahogany look over a period of time.

The upper part of the stool was always a perfect circle. The lower part formed by the four legs created a square beneath. The fusion of the square and the circle is a crucial geometrical combination in the interior spatial arrangement of the nyumba as in fig. 2.57.

Fig. 2.281; An illustration of how the square and the circle affected the interior spatial layout of the nyumba. Source: Kamenju J., 2012.

Fig. 2.283; An image showing the Maasai Knowledge Exchange. Source: Hasey M., 2015

Fig. 2.285; An image of a Maasai homestead with its flexible exterior fence, *enkang*. Source: Hasey M., 2015

2.6 Traditional architecture restatement

Most architects are acknowledging the importance of vernacular architecture. Their interest lies in not repeating what was practiced by the primitive communities since change has slowly crept into the factors that determine the architectural composition of a society i.e social order, materials and technology. However, what fascinates most professionals in the built environment is how the traditional architecture satisfied a community's needs far much better than its modern counterpart does (Denyer, 1978).

This section of the written thesis will look into attempts made by architects and professionals in the built environment to represent traditional architecture of various communities.

2.61 The Maasai Knowledge Exchange

The Maasai Knowledge Exchange, fig. 2.58, is a hub for meeting and sharing new ideas in an endeavour to educate one another. The campus provides for spaces that facilitate meetings, debates, discussions, festivities and celebrations in order to strengthen the aspect of unity in the community. The spaces incorporated include computer labs and library, private and public meeting rooms as well as interior and exterior spaces.

With the consideration that the Maasai were nomadic pastoralists and their houses were built to honour this fact, the design was thus conceptualized on the basis of flexibility. The campus' external wall mimics the *enkang* (fence), fig. 2.59, of the Maasai's homestead by surrounding the entire campus in an organic fashion. An interesting rendition is achieved by a random play of the degree of the wall's permeability that also allows for future expansion. The exterior wall represents a deliberate fusion of contemporary and traditional Maasai architecture. The series of thoughts bear fruit to a modern contemporary institution that aims to represent Maasai traditional architecture in this era.

Fig. 2.289; A drawing of the floor plan of Maasai Knowledge Exchange centre. Source: Hasey M., 2015

Fig. 2.291; An image of the computer laboratory and the library. Source: Hasey M., 2015

Floor plan

The wall system resembles the curving, wrapping and encircling nature of the Maasai Enkang as in fig. 2.60. It is built with respect to three acacia trees, surrounding the trees and carving out interior space right out of the infinite exterior space. Each of the space formed represents a mini-hub; the parliament, the communication lab and the multi-purpose social space as shown in fig. 2.60. To reinforce the social function of the campus, each hub opens up to an exterior gathering and meeting space. These social spaces house water tanks, utility and storage functions.

The approach

The institution is barely noticeable from afar as the local stone used easily blends in with the natural environment. The architect also drew from the low hanging acacia trees as well as the low floor-to-ceiling *manyattas* as the buildings' scale is in proportion with the surrounding nature.

The entrance

The winding entrance planes mimic the fluctuating enkang and the entry into a *Manyatta*. This noticeable feature was meant to keep off wild animals by confusing them.

Computer laboratory and library

The computer laboratory, fig. 2.61, aims to promote exchange of ideas and knowledge in the diverse world. It offers the Maasai a platform to learn, acquire and be competent with skills necessary in this digital era.

Meeting spaces

Exterior

The design incorporates a curving amphitheater that acts as a transition space between the entrance and the neighbouring building. Characterized by a centrally positioned acacia tree with seating spaces around and above the ground that offers remarkable views to the Maasai landscape beyond as in fig. 2.62.

Fig. 2.293; An image of the exterior meeting space. Source: Hasey M., 2015

Fig. 2.295; An image of the 400 pax. meeting space. Source: Hasey M., 2015

Fig. 2.297; A map showing the location of Sedhiou in Senegal. Source: maphill.com

Interior

The complex provides ample interior spaces for both small and large gathering groups. Both of the meeting rooms have low ceilings, a characteristic of Maasai Manyattas.

Traditionally, the Maasai people would hold meetings beneath the acacia trees, seated while surrounding it. The architect restates the traditional spatial arrangement in the modern context as in fig. 2.63. The space has a capacity of 400 people and would provide adequate sheltered space for the Maasai people to discuss important matters that influence their culture while having a glimpse of their landscape.

2.62 Sedhiou Cultural Centre, Senegal

Location and brief history

Sedhiou is a region of Senegal located on the South-West part in the Casamance natural region (fig. 2.64). From 1980 to 2005, this region has encountered tough wars with death tolls of up to 5,000 people and over 20,000 evacuees. With over seven ethnic groups (Mandinka, Balantes, Diolas, Fula, Creol, Diahanké, Mancangne) living in this part of the country, the region offers an exciting rich history and past experiences that is told through the Mandinka language with the help of the music instrument, Kora. The Griot individuals being the promoters of African culture in this area pass down the historical events of the place through storytelling and music. For a place deeply rooted in history with lack of archives and written material to preserve the stories, the purpose then became to design a contemporary structure that considers the ethnic balance of the groups living in Sedhiou and offers a platform for these communities to pass the knowledge of their rich history and culture.

The concept

Sedhiou cultural centre is a submission in the Kaira Loro international architecture competition. The project statement entailed designing a contemporary building that takes into account the vernacular spirit of the Senegalese people by preserving their architectural spirit whilst reinterpreting the local architectural language in the modern age. This need came about due to the recent influence of modernity on Senegal's architecture abandoning the vernacular architecture that did not seem to align with the people's contemporary needs. The form is an abstraction of the traditional roof while maintaining the cylindrical bottom. By cutting off a piece of the roof as shown in fig. 2.65, the designer is able to achieve a contemporary form and achieving air and light openings in the roof. The design consists of four circular zones with a play of circular forms creating different character of spaces; indoor, partial indoor and outdoor spaces that are meant to bring the different ethnic groups through socializing.

Fig. 2.299; Above: Drawings showing the abstraction of the concept into built form. Below: artistic impressions of the centre's exterior (left), and interior spaces (centre and right). Source: behance.net downloaded in October 2019

Sedhiou's Culture Centre
By interweaving vernacular architecture, urban context, and nature, the building creates a new environment that fits the local community aspirations, and suit their needs through dissolving the gap between their legacy and the modernity.

The spaces

The four different zones, fig. 2.66, to facilitate the preservation of their culture are the education space, the exhibition area, the auditorium and the support facilities of the administration, offices and restrooms.

The education zone will allow the communities and visitors to educate each other on their culture and rich history and most importantly agriculture, being the most developed economic sector in Sedhiou.

The exhibition space will showcase pictures, paintings, cultural artifacts and other pieces of artwork that tells the story of the communities' past experiences and culture in an effort to promote the education aspect of the centre.

The auditorium will further promote education by providing a space that allows the community to educate each other through songs and dances. This gives a chance for the different generations to learn about their pasts as well as find a balance with the future. The administration offices and restrooms are to support the three zones for the centre to work harmoniously.

Fig. 2.301; Above: A drawing of the centre showing the different spaces. Below: The different zones. Source: behance.net downloaded in October 2019

Materials and sustainability

The building uses local innovative materials, fig. 2.68, replacing concrete with compressed earth blocks with a thatched roof that is constructed to collect water for the community during the rainy season from June to October. The frame for the roof attachment is constructed using bamboo strips. The roof openings allow for passive air circulation, fig. 2.69, and an innovative way of bringing light into the space horizontally.

Community participation

The design allows for the use of simple materials and champions for the community to participate in its construction. This creates an attachment between the people and the place. Moreover, this makes the people acquire a sense of ownership to the place as they built it with their own hands adding onto their stories. The next generation have the same place to tell their stories making the place timeless.

Fig. 2.305; Above: An illustration showing the different materials used. Source: behance.net retrieved in October 2019.

Fig. 2.307; Below: Left: An illustration showing passive air circulation through the roof openings. Right: Elevations. Source: behance.net retrieved in October 2019.

2.63 Jean-Marie Tjibaou Cultural Center

Location and brief history

The centre is named after Jean-Marie Tjibaou who played an important role in the independence of the Kanak people from their French rulers. To pacify this relationship, the French government offered to pay for a cultural centre whose design was to be decided by a panel of judges in a competition. Architect Renzo Piano with his search to understand the Kanak traditional culture was able to design a development that impressed the judges and emerged the winning submission. The project site is in the New Caledonia in Tina peninsula surrounded by water on its three sides. New Caledonia, fig. 2.69, is a French territory that comprises of dozens of islands in the South Pacific. The area is characterized with lush vegetation that the architect wanted to maintain by creating a cluster of huts forming three villages spaced out and opening up to tree-filled spaces abundant with untouched nature as in fig. 2.70 and fig. 2.71.

Fig. 2.308; A map of New Caledonia showing the position of Jean-Marie Tjibaou Cultural Center. Source: google maps retrieved in November 2019.

Fig. 2.314; An aerial view of Jean-Marie Cultural Center showing the water surrounding it on three sides. Source: arch2o.com downloaded in October 2019.

Fig. 2.71; An artistic expression of the development showing the three villages, paths and context. Source: fourclavier.com retrieved in October 2019.

The spaces

The floor plan design, fig. 2.72, consists of ten huts, of three different sizes divided into three villages. The first village houses the exhibition spaces, the second comprises the research areas, a conference room and a library. The last series of huts are the studios for music, dance, sculpture and painting.

All these spaces are interconnected by a 250m long footpath.

The form

The buildings' form is influenced by the traditional Kanak architecture with its high roof as in fig. 2.73. The modern interpretation achieved this as the huts are ranging from 20 to 28 metres in height as in fig. 2.74. Unlike the traditional huts that were made using traditional woven vegetable fibre, the new huts were made using treated *iroko* wood on the exterior shell made of ribs and slats as in fig. 2.75. while employing the use of modern materials such as steel, glass and aluminium as in fig. 2.76. The use of the traditional wood, *iroko*, and stone was to maintain a link to the past.

Top: Fig. 2.72; The floor plan

Mid-left: Fig. 2.316; An image showing the traditional Kanak architecture against its modern interpretation.

Mid-right: Fig. 2.74: An image showing the different ranges of heights of the structures.

Bottom right: Fig. 2.75: An image showing the wooden ribs and slats that form the exterior shell of the huts.

Source: arch20.com retrieved in October 2019.

The mode of construction

Fig. 2.77 shows the construction of the traditional hut with horizontal hoops and rafter. In the same way, the same figure shows the modern restatement of this mode of construction using wooden ribs and slats. The architect was able to reinterpret the construction styles in the modern era.

Materials and sustainability

Both modern and traditional materials have been fused to create a structure that borrows from the different epochs. The *iroko* wood has been preserved with a termite-repellant treatment ensuring its low maintenance and thus longer shelf-life.

The building uses natural passive ventilation eliminating the need for mechanical means. The exterior shell consists of a double façade with wooden slats angled to harness the monsoon winds coming blowing from the sea. The slats are made up of adjustable louvers that open up when the wind is light to allow fresh air in and close when the speed of wind is high.

Fig. 2.317; An image showing the use of modern materials in the library. Source: arch2o.com

Fig. 2.323; An image of the exterior double facade made of ribs and adjustable slats. Source: arch2o.com, Oct. 2019

Fig. 2.319; An image showing the similar mode of construction between the traditional and modern huts. Source: arch2o.com, Oct. 2019

Fig. 2.321; An illustration showing passive ventilation in the building. Source: arch2o.com, Oct. 2019

CHAPTER THREE:

METHODS OF RESEARCH

Fig. 3.01; An image of Thingira Cultural Centre at Sagana. Source: thingiraculturalvillage.com, Sept. 2019

Fig. 3.02; A modern restatement of the traditional African hut. Source: archdaily.com, Sept. 2019

3.1 Introduction

This chapter aims to introduce the reader to the methods the researcher will employ in looking into buildings or centres that have aimed to reinterpret traditional Agikuyu spaces and forms such as Thingira Cultural Village as in fig. 3.01. Many processes and techniques are available for research. In order to effectively answer the research questions, specific methods will be deemed more suitable. The research methods chosen will be most applicable due to their validity and reliability as will be later explained in this section of the written thesis.

The content also explains why the research is to be carried out. In addition, a structured plan will be outlined to facilitate the research process. The most appropriate time for the research will be indicated as well. Of course the population to be researched on is bound to be revealed not forgetting the methods to be used in the collection of data and its subsequent presentation.

3.2 Research purpose

The study will take on an explanatory approach. This is an endeavour to provide answers on how Agikuyu spaces and forms have been restated in the modern context. For example, in fig. 3.02, the African hut has been reinterpreted in the modern epoch. What efforts have been undertaken to do so? More so, have these reinterpretations been successful or have they failed miserably? This is not just an ‘out of the blue’ fantasy but is rather meant to provide information on the third and final research question as earlier mentioned in the first chapter: “What efforts have been made to represent the Agikuyu traditional spaces and forms in the built environment today and how successful have they proven to be?”

An in-depth observation into spaces and forms of these ‘efforts’ will provide the researcher with the necessary information for analysis in order to accurately respond to the research objective.

Fig. 3.03; An illustration showing the research design. Source: researchgate.net, Sept. 2019

3.3 Research design

The case study method will be most appropriate for this study. It will entail looking into three places; Riuki Cultural Centre in Kiambu, Thingira Cultural Village in Sagana, fig. 3.01, and Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's house in Limuru. All these built structures found in Kenya are attempts made to represent traditional Agikuyu architecture. This method has been chosen for the following reasons:

- It allows for the collection of data in these centres in their actual and current physical state.
- It is easy to observe and understand the use of space with as little disruption as possible as the researcher becomes one with the residents.

The purpose of the case study method is to explore the physical aspect of these places. By delving into their spaces and forms, this method will provide an intense analysis on the organization of spaces, articulation of forms and the responsive physical environment surrounding these cases. Afterwards, the researcher will have adequate information to compare the data collected with the expected Agikuyu spaces and forms as outlined in Chapter Two, the literature review of Agikuyu spaces and forms, fig. 3.03.

Interviewing the Agikuyu people is part of the survey method which the researcher will adopt. As explained in the 'Background of the problem' in Chapter One, the Agikuyu people rejected an attempt by the Conarch Associates to reinterpret a modern centre in Mukurwe Wa Nyagathanga. This is because it did not represent their culture. The interviews will aim in figuring out, in their own opinions, if these places have tried to do so. From their own 'layman' understanding, it will assist to decipher the success and failures of these places.

Fig. 3.04; An illustration of the cross-sectional type of study. Source: Author, Nov. 2019

Fig. 3.05; A map of Kenya showing the Central province, the target geographical location. Source:exploringafrica.matrix.msu.edu, Nov. 2019

3.4 Time horizon of the study

The cross-sectional type of study, fig. 3.04, will be the ultimate choice. This is due to the limited amount of time allocated to research on the subject topic. The fieldwork study will be carried out from 04/09/2019 to 18/09/2019.

3.4 Population, element and population frame

The Kikuyu people of Kenya are the interest of this study. Obviously, they are the target population. Most of them reside in the Central province of Kenya, fig. 3.05. This research, however, will include the whole population of the Kikuyu people in Kenya.

3.5 Sampling design

Purposive sampling, fig. 3.06, was the most preferred non-probability method due to the little time allocated for this research. It was also selected by the researcher as it boasts of the highest probability in acquiring the best suitable results for this study.

The following factors were considered in the selection of the case studies mentioned:

- Low chances of finding Agikuyu architecture restatements in the modern era.
- Availability of relevant material on the case studies.
- Physical accessibility of the case studies.
- Level of suitability for the research topic.

3.6 Data collection

After selecting the case study and survey method, the researcher will employ both primary and secondary sources in the collection of data.

3.6.1 Primary sources

This encompasses all first-hand data obtained directly from the field. They are as follows:

Fig. 3.06; An illustration of purposive sampling. Source:tophat.com, Nov. 2019

Fig. 3.07; An image of sketches and notes used to collect data. Source: artdesign.com, Nov. 2019

Fig. 3.08; An drawing of a building's elevations. Source:landscapedesignarchitecture.yolasite.com, Nov. 2019

3.6.1.1 Observation

The researcher will utilize the act of observing in the fieldwork exercise. In doing so, she will be able to see how the residents use the spaces and note what type of spaces and forms have been designed. She will be able to perceive the activities that take place and how these spaces are designed to support them. Most importantly, after understanding the character of Agikuyu spaces and forms in Chapter Two, she will observe whether there exists some form of similarity or utter disparity.

Through observation, the researcher will document the findings by the use of photographs, notes and hand-drawn sketches.

3.6.1.1.1 Photographs

The camera is an essential piece in capturing a memory in a second. The pictures will showcase the actual spatial layouts, both exterior and interior, and the form. It is relied upon due to its authenticity.

3.6.1.1.2 Notes

Short notes, fig. 3.07, on important points will be penned down.

3.6.1.1.3 Hand-drawn sketches

Sketching the spatial layouts, the form composition, proportional 3d drawings indicating the use of spaces as well as the physical context will prove greatly functional in the analysis of data. Plans, sections and elevations, 3.08, will be drawn to offer a deep understanding of space relationships.

3.6.1.2 Interviews

Structured interviews will be prepared before visiting the various places. The questions asked will revolve around the people's opinion on what represents Agikuyu in the built environment. What is the image of an Agikuyu cultural place? Rather, what would the Agikuyu laymen familiarize as

Fig. 3.09; A screenshot of Routledge's book. Source: Routledge S., 1910

Fig. 3.10; An image showing a comparative analysis of traditional vs modern. Source: awayfromafrica.com, Nov. 2019

their place? What do they expect to find? What would draw them closer to such places? In other words, what image would capture their sight and seem unconsciously familiar to their existence? Which image would they accept and which would they uncompromisingly reject?

3.6.2 Secondary sources

The secondary sources used have been retrieved from the internet in form of published e-journals and papers. Published books such as Routledge's '*With a Prehistoric people: The Akikuyu of British East Africa*', fig. 3.09, have contributed immensely in assembling this written thesis. Moreover, the author has looked at unpublished works; mainly past written thesis related to space and form making in the broader context and others narrowed down into Agikuyu architecture.

This written thesis is in part a sum of the knowledge obtained from these sources. The information obtained has supported the author's thought process and provided relevant information on the research topic.

3.7 Data analysis

Analyzing data involves processing collected data obtained from the field into important information that will guide the author in answering the research questions and concluding the dissertation whilst providing recommendations.

3.7.1 Comparative analysis

The data collected on the spatial organization layouts and form designs of the mentioned case studies will be put against the expected equivalents of the same in the Agikuyu traditional culture as in Chapter Two. By comparing the two, fig. 3.10, the researcher will be able to analyze if the design of the places were inspired by traditional Agikuyu architecture.

The following variables will be used in the comparison:

- Spatial layouts

Fig. 3.11; A map of Kenya showing the forty-seven counties. Source: tuko.co.ke, Nov. 2019

Fig. 3.12; An image of CAD drawings. Source: caddrawing.org, Nov. 2019

- Form
- Use of space
- Materials

3.8 Data presentation

After analysis, the data is then presented using specific ways in order to make it easily understandable and enable the researcher to finalize on answering the required research question. The following materials will be adopted in presenting the data:

3.8.1 Maps

These will be used to point out the location of the case studies vis a vie the broader Kenyan context. Fig. 3.11 shows the forty-seven counties of Kenya under the 2010 constitution of Kenya. Each of the case studies is part of the forty-seven counties.

3.8.2 Sketches

Hand drawn sketches of spatial layouts, forms and necessary details will be computer modified by using CAD software to convey more presentable and better communicative drawings, fig.3.12.

3.8.3 Descriptive text

Words will be important in describing the approach into the different places (case studies), their aura, the surrounding context and linking the various content to achieve a rich dissertation.

3.8.4 Photographs

These images will capture the exact physical conditions of the places. The pictures will be displayed to support and break the monotony of the descriptive text.

**CHAPTER
FOUR:**

ANALYZING THE FINDINGS

Fig. 4.01; A photograph of Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.02; A photograph of Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.03; A photograph of Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's house in Limuru. Source: Author, Sept. 2019.

4.1 Introduction

" It is full in all its provinces of the clearest indications that Society in primitive times was not, what it is assumed to be at present, a collection of individuals. In fact, and in view of the men who composed it, it was an aggregation of families." (Routledge,1910)

The preliminary chapters have tactically responded to two of the three research objectives; how Agikuyu spaces and forms were created, and what practices led to this generation of spaces. Gradually, the literature has paved the way for this chapter to answer the final question: "What efforts have been made to represent the Agikuyu traditional spaces and forms in the built environment today and how successful have they proven to be?"

This part of the written thesis aims to showcase the information collected on Riuki Cultural Centre in Kiambu (Fig 4.01), Thingira Cultural Village in Sagana (Fig 4.02) as well as the Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's House in Limuru (Fig 4.03). These are restatements of the Agikuyu traditional architecture. The information gathered will then be put against the Agikuyu traditional architecture in an effort to realize the similarities and differences in the spaces and forms made. By using a comparative analysis, the author will ascertain whether the design of these places have been inspired by the old established Agikuyu architecture.

Certain parameters have been adopted to facilitate this comparative analysis. These variables are the spatial layouts, form analysis, the use of space and materials and technology.

4.2 Case study one: Thingira Cultural Village, Sagana, Kenya

4.21 Location and brief history

Thingira Cultural Village is a cultural centre situated in Kirinyaga county, fig. 4.05, Kenya. The place is located along Nairobi-Nyeri highway as you head to Sagana town, fig. 4.07. The climate is unbearably hot with a semi-arid environment characterized by scanty bushes and thorny trees. This vegetation lines the welcome trail into the cultural site.

As earlier stated, the thingira is simply a Gikuyu man's hut. The cultural village is a composition of four different homesteads, fig. 4.08, of communities that reside around the Mt. Kenya region; the Embu, Meru, Kikuyu and the Kamba. The Kikuyu homestead was built in 2012, the Meru followed shortly thereafter while the Embu and Kamba are still under construction. All these ideas are accredited to one Leah Wangeci Njoroge, a cultural ambassador who wanted to preserve the material culture of the people residing around the Mt. Kenya region.

Fig. 4.04; A map of the world showing the location of Kenya. Source: facts.co, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.05; The map of Kenya showing the location of Kirinyaga county. Source: learn.e-limu.org, Nov. 2019

Fig. 4.07; A map of Kirinyaga County showing the location of Sagana, Kerugoya and Wanguru towns. Source: learn.e-limu.org, Nov. 2019

Fig. 4.06; An image showing the location of Thingira Cultural Village in relation to Sagana town. Source: google maps, Nov. 2019

4.22 The site plan

The Kikuyu homestead is built as a mimic of the traditional homestead. It is mainly used as a showcase of how the traditional homestead looked like. It is therefore a resourceful tool in cultural education.

However, no one resides in the Kikuyu huts and this proves difficult as the space loses its realistic ability.

The Embu and Kamba homesteads are still under construction. Modern materials such as stone and concrete have been used.

The Meru homestead is habitable. Guests who are in need of accommodation are encouraged to rent out a room in this homestead.

By renting out spaces, the facility is able to financially support its maintenance. The crocodile park, fig. 4.12, also contributes to the financial situation of the cultural village. In addition, the entrance fees as well as offering restaurant services in the performance hall factors greatly in the continuity of the cultural village.

Fig. 4.08; Plan of the Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.10; A photograph of the Embu homestead. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.09; A photograph of the Kamba homestead. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.11; A photograph of the Meru homestead. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

The performance hall, fig. 4.13, also acts as the dining area. Behind this space is the kitchen. The performance hall opens to outdoor seating areas on either side. The kitchen serves traditional food and drinks such as *muratina*, traditional beer, which people enjoy under the shade of the mango trees as in fig. 4.14. The mango trees are native to this area. They provide food for the employees and can also be sold off. It is therefore income generating for the cultural village to sustain such trees.

The village represents the peaceful co-existence of the different communities around Mount Kenya. The location of the site proves to be appropriate as Thingira Cultural Village is only 69.8 kilometres to Mount Kenya.

For the purposes of this study, the author will look into the Kikuyu homestead which is in part the main target of this study.

Fig. 4.13; A photograph of the performance hall. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.12; A photograph of the Thingira crocodile park. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.14; A photograph of two men enjoying *muratina* under the mango trees. Source: Author. Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.15; A panoramic view of the village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

4.23 Data Analysis

4.231 Spatial layout

Fig. 4.16; A plan of a traditional *mucii* homestead. Source: thingiraculturalvillage.com, Sept. 2019.

Fig. 4.18; A plan of the Kikuyu homestead at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.19; An image of the *nja* at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

4.2311 Similarities

Presence of the Nja

In both homesteads, fig. 4.16 and fig. 4.17, the houses encircle a central space at the centre of the space. The *nja* (courtyard), fig. 4.18, is partly bare earth with a patch of grass slowly encroaching the space. In the traditional Agikuyu setting, the *nja* was always bare earth. No grass could have

Fig. 4.20; A photograph of the first wife's *nyumba* and her *nyakiambi*. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.21; An illustration of the entrance and the sons' *thingiras* at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019.

survived the daily traffic of people, cattle and goats moving in the space. However, considering the huts are uninhabitable, the movement of people is minimal.

The *nja* acts as the datum in both homesteads. All the entrances have a direct connection to the space.

Position of the *nyakiambi*

The *nyakiambi*, the first wife's granary, was at times closest to her hut in the traditional context. In other homesteads, her granaries were situated on either side of the *nja*'s entrance. The Kikuyu homestead at Thingira Cultural Village, fig. 4.19, further exemplifies this concept.

Placement of the Sons' *thingiras* (huts)

These were always in close proximity to the entrance as in fig 4.20. In both homesteads, the case is the same.

Two entrances and exits

This was not common in all traditional typologies. However, some homesteads were designed to allow for a back entrance.

Circular-shaped plans

In both cases, the huts reveal a circular plan as in fig. 4.16 and 4.17. Considered highly popular among the African communities, the circular-shaped plan was believed to prevent night-runners from finding the entrance of the house as they would repeatedly go round and round the circumference of the hut in a confused state. Nevertheless, the interior spatial arrangement of the huts of different communities as well as the form would always differ. This will be later discussed in this chapter.

Fig. 4.22; A photograph of the kitchen at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.23; An image showing the position of the granaries, *ikumbi*. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

4.2312 Differences

Position of the first wife's nyumba

The first wife's house was mostly positioned directly opposite the main entrance in the Agikuyu traditional setting. However, that may not be the case as it is off tangent in the Thingira Cultural Village set-up.

The cattle shed

The absence of the cattle shed in the Kikuyu homestead at the Thingira Cultural Village is highly anticipated due to the loss in value of cattle in the modern times. In the Agikuyu traditional context, however, cattle were a very important source of wealth. They were greatly instrumental in paying dowry, providence of food especially during ceremonies and an immense show of pride. Times have changed and the standard measure of wealth is currently money.

The kitchen

The presence of the kitchen, fig. 4.21, as its own standing structure was never a spatial characteristic of the Agikuyu traditional architecture. Overtime, spaces became more separated and differentiated consequently resulting in the creation of more spaces. For instance, a modern house would comprise of many spaces as compared to a traditional house. In the old Agikuyu context, the kitchen (*riko*) was always situated at the centre of the *nyumba* (the woman's hut) easily identified by the presence of three stones used to support the cooking pot.

Position of the *ikumbi*, granaries

Each wife owned at least one granary. It is therefore safe to assume that the other two *ikumbi* situated on the left side of the entrance belong to the other two wives. In the older spatial layout, each wife's *ikumbi* was always located closest to her *nyumba*. This may not be the case in the layout showcased at Thingira Cultural Village as in fig 4.22.

4.2313 Kihingo, Thome and Nja

The arrangement of these spaces in progression as from kihingo, thome to the nja mimics the traditional planning concept. Kihingo is the gate, thome is the large area where visitors are welcomed and nja, the courtyard as in fig. 4.23 and 4.24.

4.232 The form

The Entrance

These spaces still play a huge role in our society today. We need fortifications, *kihingo*, from our untrustworthy neighbours. We still have to welcome our neighbours, *thome*, and most buildings, influenced by the Ubuntu concept as in Chapter Two of this thesis, seem to pay respect to a central space, the *nja*. However, the treatment of the kihingo, rather its form, especially at Thingira Cultural Village is completely different. A form of a grove-like feature was prominent as in fig. 4.25 in the traditional setting. In fig. 4.26, the entrance is open to sky unlike its traditional counterpart in 4.25 which was mostly enclosed or partially open to sky.

This distinct character of this space has been ignored. In the hot climate of Sagana, this feature would have

Thingira cultural village

Fig. 4.24; An image showing the *kihingo*, *thome* and *nja* at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Agikuyu traditional setting

Fig. 4.25; An image showing the *kihingo*, *thome* and *nja* in the traditional setting. Source: Anyamba T., 1994.

Fig. 4.27; An image illustrating the character of the *kihingo* at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019.

Fig. 4.26; An image illustrating the character of the *kihingo* in the traditional setting. Source: Routledge, 1910

Height

The vertical distance from the floor-to-eaves is 1750mm high as in fig. 4.27. The traditional wall construction consisted of planks of about 6feet, approximately 1800mm. However, earlier photographs from the Il Popolo suggest that the floor-to-eaves height was even shorter than 1.8metres. Fig. 4.29 shows how the height of the men was even higher than the height from the floor to the roof eaves. This would mean that one would have to bend to access the *muromo*, doorway. Fig. 4.28 shows the vertical height allowance for passage was almost equated to that of a goat.

Fig. 4.30; An illustration showing the height allowance of the hut in comparison to that of a man. Source: Il Popolo

Fig. 4.28; An image showing the height allowance of the huts at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.29; An image of the height allowance of a man equated to almost that of a goat. Source: Routledge, 1910

The Form of the Nyumba

Muromo, doorway

The nyumba at the thingira cultural village provides for 800mm width to the muromo as in fig. 4.31. The traditional one at about 600mm, is narrower by 200mm as in fig. 4.32.

Size

Fig. 4.33 and 4.34 show the differing diameters of the nyumbas built in different eras. The nyumba at Thingira Cultural Village measures about 4000mm (13feet), 2feet less compared to the traditional nyumba that was never less than 4600mm (15feet) in diameter. The nyumba's diameter always varied between 15 to 20feet in diameter, within 4600mm and 6100mm.

Githaku, entrance porch

In the traditional setting, the githaku was a distinct feature in its form identification. It was a space where the woman could entertain her guests, store her boiling pots and even cook food especially during the day. The form of the Kikuyu nyumba at the Thingira Cultural Village does not mimic this unique characteristic. The door is directly open to the nja as in fig. 4.31 with no defined space below the overhang.

Fig. 4.31; An image of the nyumba at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.32; A sketch of the traditional nyumba. Source: Anyamba, 2004.

Fig. 4.34; A section through the nyumba at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.33; A section through the traditional nyumba. Source: Kamenju, 2012.

This may be because no one lives in the Kikuyu huts. Nevertheless, the caretaker, a Kikuyu man, suggests otherwise. He says that the variation in form was as a result of variation in customs. This coincides with Routledge's (1910) point as he experienced difficulty in gathering information on the Kikuyu tribe. As he put it, "*the difficulty arose in part from the fact that there are undoubtedly variations of customs in different districts*". With variations of customs comes variations in form. A house in Kiambu would thus look different from that in Nyeri.

Mucobe, spikes

The thingiras, nyumbas and ikumbi in a mucii always embodied a common mark, the presence of a *mucobe* positioned at the exterior apex of the roof as in fig. 4.35.

This detail was considered in the design of the huts in the mucii at the Thingira Cultural Village as in fig. 4.34.

Shape

The circular plans translated into a cylindrical form very common among many African communities. The huts at Thingira Cultural Village resemble the traditional huts with their cylindrical bottom and the conical roofs as in fig. 4.37.

Fig. 4.36; A image showing the spikes on the huts at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.37; An image of the roof at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

The Roof

In fig. 4.33, the section of the nyumba at the Thingira Cultural Village shows the lack of interior columns prominent in the design of the nyumba. With the absence of these poles results the absence of the beams that were a characteristic of the traditional nyumba. These beams were essential in the interior spatial arrangement of the nyumba as in fig. 2.23. The introduction of a polythene paper at Thingira Cultural Village, fig. 4.37, was to prevent the soil from the termites' mounds on the roof from falling into the interior spaces. In the traditional nyumba, however, no termites could withstand the smoke from the fireplace.

Fig. 4.35; An image of a traditional homestead showing spikes on top of the huts. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu

Fig. 4.38; An image of the traditional roof. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu

4.233 Use of space

The Nja

This bare earthed central space housed numerous activities. From the crushing of grains using the grinding stone and the mortar and pestle, to the dancing performances and children plays not forgetting the storytelling sessions mostly done in the evenings.

In an effort to introduce these customs in the modern epoch, Thingira Cultural Village educates their visitors on the Kikuyu old practices. For instance, the guests are welcomed into the nja and encouraged to participate in the dances showcased as in fig. 4.39.

Afterwards, standing or seated in the same space as illustrated in fig. 4.45, they are enlightened of the Kikuyu customs of birth, initiation, marriage and death. They are later shown the traditional way of lighting a fire using sticks, the crushing of grains using the grinding stone, fig. 4.41, and the pestle and mortar all the while being participants rather than spectators. The elders and dancers that conduct these cultural education sessions are from the community nearby.

Thingira cultural village

Fig. 4.40; An image of visitors and elders dancing at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: instagram.com, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.41; An image of a woman grinding grains at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: instagram.com, Sept. 2019

Agikuyu traditional setting

Fig. 4.39; An image of warriors dancing in the traditional setting. Source: Routledge, 1910.

Fig. 4.42; An image of a Gikuyu woman grinding grains while her children are watching. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu.

The elder sits or stands at the centre of the circle. The grinding stone, mortar and pestle and the gourds are placed around him. The shorter children are seated in a circular arrangement and the taller kids are standing behind them as in Fig. 4.45. This illustration mimics the spatial arrangement of the *Gichukia* dance as in fig. 4.44.

In both cases, the spatial arrangement of the learners depends on a central element, the *Mukuyu* tree and the elder. The *Mukuyu* tree and the elder are thus the axis. Everything else begins from their position and revolves around them. This resembles the cosmology of the *kiondo* inspired by the spiral of life as discussed in Chapter Two. The making of the *kiondo* commences from the navel to infinity. The wefts and warps surround the navel, the centre. The navel is the *Mukuyu* tree in the *Gichukia* dance and the elder in the spatial arrangement of the dance at Thingira Cultural Village.

Fig. 4.44; An image of an elder educating the visitors on their traditions. Source: instagram.com, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.46; An illustration of the spatial arrangement at Thingira Cultural Village during a cultural education session. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.43; An image of a traditional dance. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu

Fig. 4.45; An illustration of the spatial arrangement of the *Gichukia* dance. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

4.234 Materials

At Thingira Cultural Village, most of the huts in the Kikuyu homestead are constructed with young saplings tied together finished with mud and plastered with clay as in fig. 4.46. The roof is constructed using wooden rafters and finished with dry grass as thatch. Some of the huts have been left with the young saplings tied together forming a brushwood wall. This wall resembles the one in fig. 4.47 in a traditional setting.

For a development built in 2012, the designer should have considered modern materials to give the building a meaning in its time. Modern materials such as steel and various modern wood finishes would have made the structures more aesthetically appealing and therefore attractive to more guests. Different building technologies would give the development a place in its time. The interviewee, however, stated that the aim of the designer was to mimic the traditional Kikuyu homestead with an aim of educating the visitors of the Agikuyu traditional life.

Fig. 4.47; An illustration of the materials used at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.48; An illustration of the materials used in a traditional hut. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu retrieved in Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.49; The location of Kenya in the global context. Source: freeworldmaps.net, Nov. 2019

4.3 Case study two: Ngugi wa Thiong'o's house in Kamirithu, Limuru

4.31 Location and brief history

Ngugi Wa Thiong'o is a prolific writer born in Kamirithu, Limuru, Kenya. What is most unique about his popular writing is how he tirelessly advocates for African renaissance. His books are a constant reminder of the love he possesses for his Kikuyu language in an effort to urge fellow Africans to appreciate their ethnic languages over European languages. He is a professor of Literature and championed for the change of the department's name from Department of English to the Department of Literature at the University of Nairobi where he lectured till 1977. This was to promote the studying of other languages apart from English.

Kamirithu, fig. 4.51, is a past colonial village located in Limuru, Kiambu County, fig. 4.50, in Kenya. This area is part of the White Kenya highlands where the British settled from 1895 to independence day in 1963. It also boasts as the birthplace of Ngugi Wa Thiong'o. Ngugi lived through the colonial period and being an adolescent, he witnessed the Mau Mau war of independence (1952-1962). This experience inspired his early works.

Fig. 4.50; The location of Kiambu County in the Kenyan map. Source: kiambu.go.ke, Nov. 2019

Fig. 4.52; A map of Kiambu County and its twelve constituencies. Source: kiambu.go.ke, Nov. 2019

Fig. 4.51; An image showing Kamirithu area in Limuru. Source: googlemaps.com, Nov. 2019

Fig. 4.53; An image of Ngugi Wa Thiong'o.
Source: hivisasa.com, Nov. 2019

With this little background you would then understand why he would not settle for a house that did not portray the restoration of African culture, especially his Kikuyu culture. This explains why in 1974, Arch. George Nyanja was assigned to design a house for Ngugi that would be a restatement of the traditional Agikuyu architecture. The brief entailed housing a renowned professor of literature who appreciated the benefits of modern technology and his traditional Kikuyu culture. The architect would then have to merge the old with the new.

In 1977, Ngugi, fig. 4.52, and the villagers established the Kamirithu Educational and Cultural Center in Limuru. The center was in form of an open air theatre that saw actors perform plays written in Kikuyu and directed by Ngugi and his friend Ngugi Wa Mirii. These plays touched on the aggravating political situation caused by the post-colonial government and referenced on the famous Mau Mau rebellion. Buses of university students and villagers from far travelled to watch the plays. The plays did not have trained actors but rather villagers from peasant families were performers. The shows garnered critical acclaim but only for a short period of time. The then government being highly intolerant to criticism captured Ngugi Wa Thiong'o and destroyed the theatre in 1982. Fig. 4.53 shows a New York Times article about the closure of the Kamirithu Centre by the government. He was later released but rumours of his intended demise were up in the air.

In 1982, Ngugi fled to exile and left his wife in charge of the house. In 1996, his wife passed on and his brother took care of the house. Later, his nephew moved in with his wife and two kids and are currently residing in the house. Owing to the decades it has on its shelf, the house is undergoing renovations while the inhabitants are still living within.

Fig. 4.54; A screenshot of the New York Times article about the closure of Kamirithu Educational and Cultural Center in 1982.
Source: nytimes.com, Nov. 2019

4.32 Data analysis

4.321 Spatial layout

Fig. 4.55; A plan of the traditional Kikuyu homestead. Source: Kamenju J., 2012.

Fig. 4.56; A plan of Ngugi Wa Thiongo's estate. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Similarities

The *nja*

In both layouts, Ngugi's House and the typical traditional homestead, houses are arranged around a central space. The *Nja* is the datum. The character of the *Nja* in the traditional setting was bare earth as in fig. 4.57. The grass could not grow due to the constant traffic of people and goats in this space. To depict this feature, concrete tiles were laid out on the floor of the *Nja* in Ngugi's house as in fig. 4.56.

Kihingo, Thome and *Nja*

Kihingo is the gate. Thome is a large space into the *mucii*, homestead, where visitors are welcomed into. They are then directed into the *nja* by the resident of that *mucii*. In the spatial layout of Ngugi's compound, the subsequent order of these spaces is emulated as in fig. 4.59.

The Outer and Inner Enclosures

In the traditional setting, fig. 4.23, two enclosures were popular in most homesteads. This was a division between the houses and the farming land. The inner fence, sometimes implied rather than defined as in Fig, enclosed the huts and the immediate spaces around it. The outer fence defined the boundary of that *mucii*. The space between the inner and outer fence was used for agriculture. It also played the part of a toilet/latrine as the residents relieved themselves in this space. The garbage heap was also located in this space just outside the inner fence in both layouts. Even more importantly, this space allowed for future expansion as the son's and grandson's courtyards could be extended into it. At Ngugi's, the two fences depict the traditional layout. The houses are within the inner fence and the farming land is between the inner and outer fence as in fig. 4.55. The inner fence is used as a hanging line as in fig. 4.60.

Ngugi's house

Fig. 4.58; An image of the *nja* at Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's house. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Agikuyu traditional setting

Fig. 4.57; An image of the *nja* in a traditional homestead. Source: pinterest.com, Sept.

Fig. 4.60; An illustration of the *kihingo*, *thome* and *nja* at Ngugi's house. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.59; An illustration of *kihingo*, *thome* and *nja* in the traditional homestead. Source: mukuyu.wordpress.com, Sept. 2019

The space between the inner and outer fence was used for agriculture. It also played the part of a toilet/latrine as the residents relieved themselves in this space. The garbage heap was also located in this space just outside the inner fence in both layouts. Even more importantly, this space allowed for future expansion as the son's and grandson's courtyards could be extended into it. At Ngugi's, the two fences depict the traditional layout. The houses are within the inner fence and the farming land is between the inner and outer fence as in fig. 4.55. The inner fence is used as a hanging line as in fig. 4.60.

Fig. 4.61; An image of the wire-meshed inner fence. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.62; An image of Ngugi Wa Thiongo's house in Limuru. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.63; An image of the circular fence of the traditional homestead. Source: Routledge, 1910.

Circular-shaped plans

Both the layouts display the use of circular plans of the huts. Ngugi's house consists of three circular huts that are joined together as in fig. 4.60.

Differences

Shape of the fence

In the traditional setting, homesteads had a circular outer hedge, matura, that defined its edge. Colonization resulted in orthogonal divisions of land. Land attained more value. The Kikuyu man, being an agriculturalist, fenced every inch of his piece of land to cultivate it in the hope of achieving its maximum value. The fence no longer defined the boundary but the boundary then defined the shape of the fence. And Ngugi's fence became rectangular compared to the circular hedge that was popular in the olden days. Modern materials such as iron have been invented. In fig. 4.60, the inner fence is made of a wire mesh contrary to the traditional fence made of a plant hedge.

Separation of spaces

The mucii boasted of many huts. A wealthy man's mucii would consist of more huts as compared to that of a poor man's. Each wife would have her own nyumba and at least one granary. The man has his thingira and his sons, theirs. Basically, every adult except an unmarried woman had his or her hut. Traditional customs and beliefs have been abandoned. The culture has changed. In Ngugi's house, all these adults live in the same house; a house that consists of three huts merged organically and divided into rooms that represent traditional huts. The son has his room, Ngugi and his wife share a room referred to as a Master Bedroom and even the guests have their own rooms. Granaries are now study rooms only that they keep more and more books written by the professor owing to occupational changes.

Interior spatial layout

Fig. 4.66; An interior spatial layout at Ngugi's house. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.64; An interior spatial layout of the traditional nyumba. Source: mukuyu.wordpress.com, Sept. 2019

Similarities

- Circular plans.
- The muromo and the *nja*. The doorway, muromo, opens directly into the *nja* in both layouts.
- Presence of the porch, *githaku*. The *githaku* was the distinctive feature in the design of the traditional *nyumba*. All the other huts did not have this characteristic. The porch is 1650mm wide at Ngugi's house.
- Presence of the entrance lobby and screen, *ruri*. The transitional space and screen is factored in the design of Ngugi's house. Traditionally, the screen was made of planks preventing a direct view from the *nja* into the *nyumba*. In other words, it created privacy for the residents of the *nyumba*.

Fig. 4.67; The position of the fireplace at Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's house. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.68; The square and the circle planning concept in the traditional *nyumba*. Source: pinterest.com, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.69; A photograph of a room in Ngugi's house. Source: Author, Sept. 2019.

DIFFERENCES

Position of the fireplace

In the traditional setting, the fireplace was the centerpiece of the interior spatial arrangement in the Agikuyu huts as in fig. 4.64. However, in Ngugi's house that is not the case. The fireplace is only in the living room and not a part of the interior disposition of the other huts. It is positioned on the periphery of the living room as in fig. 4.63 and fig. 4.65.

The square and the circle

The traditional *nyumba* exemplified a simple yet complex concept that defined the interior layout of the spaces. The spaces were largely a product of the fusion between the circular plan and the square formed by the beams overhead as in fig. 4.66. In the interior spatial layout of Ngugi's house, fig. 4.63, this important design feature was not considered. Some of the interior walls are curvy making the interior spaces organic in shape. This consequently results in spaces that are difficult to fit in the standard sizes of the furniture available leaving lots of dead spaces and therefore, little usable space as in fig. 4.67.

Identification of the huts

It was always easy to identify the *nyumba* from the *thingira*. The granaries, *ikumbi*, were even more distinct. The *nyumba* had a porch, the *thingira* did not. It was always bigger owing to more activities it housed in comparison with the *thingira*. At Ngugi's, the huts are almost the same size varying minimally in diameter. The biggest is 27feet while the other two are 24feet. Visually, this difference is unnoticeable and from the mere look of it, one cannot differentiate which hut represents the *nyumba* and which one depicts the *thingira*.

4.322 The form

The Entrance

The entrance into the mucii in the traditional setting was fortified with sticks or bananas or trees forming a grove-like pathway as in fig. 2.45. This was popular especially among the Kikuyus who neighboured the Maasai as a defense mechanism due to their love-hate relationship.

The entry pathway into Ngugi's compound is lined with cypress trees on either side. With the gradual growth of the trees, a grove-like enclosure has begun forming as the length of the branches increases at the upper levels, fig. 4.68. This feature mimics the entrance into a mucii in a traditional village.

This gives the entrance a distinct characteristic. It is enclosed at the upper levels. However, the traditional entrance was narrow while the entrance at Ngugi's is wide as illustrated in fig. 4.68 and 4.69. The increase in width is to accommodate the motor vehicle which is a modern invention.

Height

The traditional hut had a little height allowance that necessitated the user to stoop while entering it as in fig. 4.70. Ngugi's house offers a 3000mm floor-to-ceiling height to allow the users of the space ease of access without bending, fig. 4.71.

Traditionally, design of houses was done by the people. Today, the architect is trained to consider the human scale in the design of the houses as in the case of Ngugi's.

Fig. 4.71; The entrance into Ngugi's compound. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.70; The entrance into a traditional homestead, *mucii*. Source: Kamenju J., 2012

Fig. 4.73; An illustration of height allowance at Ngugi's house. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.72; An illustration of height allowance of a traditional hut. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu, Sept. 2019

The Form of the Nyumba

Muromo, doorway

The doorway at Ngugi's seems to be twice the width of the traditional one as in fig. 4.72 and fig. 4.73.

Size

The traditional nyumba was approximately 6000mm in diameter. At Ngugi's, one circular hut measures 8200mm and the other two are about 7300mm in diameter. Ngugi's huts are bigger in size than the traditional nyumba.

Githaku, the porch

The distinctive characteristic of the traditional nyumba, fig. 4.74, is that it had a defined space supported by columns only on the front part. This space was useful in storage, welcoming visitors and relaxing under the shade in the hot sun.

Ngugi's house in Limuru illustrates this unique feature as the entrance porch is used to unify the three huts. Its steel columns are deliberately placed only at the front part as with the traditional nyumba.

Mucobe, spikes

The traditional Kikuyu huts had a spike at the top as in fig. 4.74. The huts that comprise Ngugi's residence do not possess a spike at the top.

Fig. 4.75; An illustration of the doorway allowance at Ngugi's house. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.74; An illustration of the doorway allowance of a traditional nyumba. Source: researchgate.net, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.77; An image of Ngugi's house. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.76; An image of the traditional nyumba. Source: pinterest.com, Sept. 2019

The Roof

The traditional roof was an imperfect cone made using no instruments of measurements but the eye as a guide. This resulted in poor workmanship. For instance, the edges of eaves were not finished well and formed a zig-zag pattern around the huts. When one looks at Ngugi's cone-shaped roofs, they seem visually perfect apart from the rugged finish of the roof shingles. The edges of the eaves have been done almost perfectly. Modern instruments and specialization of different works has enabled contractors come up with innovative ways of achieving perfect shapes and forms as in Ngugi's house. The introduction of the flat roofs linking the three cones is also a modern addition to the roof design. Never did traditional Kikuyu huts have flat roofs as in fig. The interior part of the roof is finished with pvc ceilings and painted concrete ceilings. The introduction of the ceiling obscures the view of the roof framework which was always left bare in the traditional one as in fig.

4.323 Use of space

The Nja

The Nja housed lots of activities. In Ngugi's case, it acts as a relaxation space as in fig. Fig. is an artistic illustration done showing young men relaxing in the nja. The drying of grains is also done in this space.

Fig. 4.79; An illustration of the roof at Ngugi's residence. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.83; An illustration of the ceiling at Ngugi's house. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.81; An image of a man relaxing in the *nja* at Ngugi's residence. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.78; An illustration of the traditional roof. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.82; An image of the traditional roof. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.80; An image of men relaxing in the traditional *nja*. Source: pinterest.com, Sept. 2019

4.324 Materials

What is most interesting to note is the variety of materials used in the design of Ngugi's house. When one looks at the traditional hut, the materials were mainly wood in form of young thin saplings, leaves and twigs and grass. The floor was left as it is and mostly just swept. No windows hence no materials to define the openings. On the contrary, Ngugi's house is a great example of what invention of modern materials can do to transform the aesthetics of a building. From the use of glass, concrete, metal to wood and the eye appealing brick material. It is therefore safe to conclude that Agikuyu traditional structures used materials for functional purposes only while modern structures such as Ngugi's house consider the aesthetic aspect. For example, Ngugi's house would have still functioned perfectly without the brick cladding.

Traditional Agikuyu structures depended on the ease of availability of materials. Materials such as glass that were not easily available would not have been found in these huts. This is the reason why these ancient structures have been proven to be the most sustainable as compared to their modern counterparts.

Fig. 4.84; An image showing the materials used at Ngugi's house. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.85; An image showing the materials used in a traditional hut. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.86; A map of the world showing the location of Kenya. Source: worldatlas.com, Nov. 2019

Fig. 4.89; A map of Kenya showing the location of Kiambu County. Source: kiambu.go.ke, Nov. 2019

4.4 Case study three: Riuki Cultural Centre, Kiambu

4.41 Location and brief history

Riuki Cultural Centre is located in the heart of Karia town in Kiambu County in Kenya. Karia town is a small rural town in Githunguri ward of Kiambu County. The cultural centre is situated approximately 31km from Nairobi, the capital city of Kenya. It was started in 1988 by one Dr. Kinuthia, a social science graduate. Riuki means hearth or the centre. In this situation, it stands for the centre of a Gikuyu homestead. The centre offers a showcase of Agikuyu traditional architecture in its rawest form. The visitors are treated to traditional songs and dances, foods, storytelling sessions and a tour around the traditional huts that have no one residing in them. Most of the visitors happen to be foreigners and only a few are from the Kikuyu tribe and other Kenyan communities. This is contrary to what Dr. Kinuthia had hoped it to be. As he put it, he envisioned the place as an educational center rather than a tourist one. After he passed on, the maintenance of the facility spiraled down as will be seen later.

Fig. 4.88; A map of Kiambu County with the location of Githunguri ward. Source: maphill.com, Nov. 2019

Fig. 4.87; The location of Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: googlemaps.com, Nov. 2019

DATA ANALYSIS
SPATIAL ARRANGEMENT

Fig. 4.90; Layout plan of Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.91; Layout plan of a traditional homestead. Source: Mbugua J., 2014

Fig. 4.92; The Nja at Riuki Cultural Centre.
Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.93; An image of the gatehouse at Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.94; An image of the gatehouse at Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

SIMILARITIES

Presence of the Nja

In both layouts, the Nja is the central element. Everything else is positioned around it. In Riuki Cultural Centre, the space is covered with grass unlike the one in the traditional setting that was always bare earth. The spaces adjacent to the huts are however, bare earth.

Nyumbas and ikumbi

Each wife had her own nyumba. Each wife had at least one granary, ikumbi. The number of nyumbas will therefore either equal that of the ikumbi or be less than. However, the number of nyumbas cannot exceed the number of the ikumbi. This is evident in both layouts. At Riuki Cultural Centre, the two ikumbi represent the existent of two wives living in the two nyumbas. In the traditional setting in Fig., there are three ikumbi exceeding the number of wives or rather nyumbas. This means that one of the wives has two ikumbi.

The Gate House and the Young Men's Thingira

In some traditional homesteads, the young men's thingira was always positioned close to the entrance as in Fig. In Riuki Cultural Centre, instead of the young men's thingira, the gatehouse is located at the same position. The gatehouse was built a little bit later as compared to the huts in the homestead. It is made of stone unlike the huts that are walled with mud and sticks. Whether intentionally or coincidental, the gatehouse is a modern interpretation of the young men's thingira due to its strategic positioning and its relation in size. The thingira had an approximate diameter of 12-15 feet according to Leakey. The gatehouse at Riuki is 12 feet in diameter.

The shamba

DIFFERENCES

Fig. 4.95; An image of the gatehouse at Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.97; An image of the gatehouse at Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.96; An image of the gatehouse at Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

THE FORM

The Entrance

At Riuki, the entrance is characterized by a 1200mm high hedge on either side of a 3500mm wide pathway. No grove-like entry is encountered as in the traditional Agikuyu village setting.

Height

Traditionally, the height allowance for the hut was too low and entering it would have required one to bend. In Riuki, the height allowance is about 1700mm accommodating the height of most people. Entering it did not require one to bend.

Form of the Nyumba

Doorway, muromo

The size of the muromo is 750mm. The traditional muromo is narrower by 150mm.

Size

The width of the nyumbas at Riuki are approximately 16feet, 4800mm. The traditional nyumba was about 15-20feet, 4500mm to 6000mm. The measurements of the huts at Riuki range within the measurements of the traditional nyumba. The size of the thingira is 14.4feet, 4300mm. The traditional thingira ranges within the same size, 12-15feet.

Fig. 4.98; An image of the entrance open to sky. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.99; An image of the traditional entrance enclosed on the upper levels. Source: Kamenju J., 2013

Fig. 4.100; An image of the muromo at Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.101; An image of a man getting out of the traditional Agikuyu hut. Source: dailymail.co.uk, Sept. 2019

Githaku, entrance porch

The traditional *nyumba* was very distinctive because of its front porch, *githaku*. The *nyumbas* at Riuki Cultural Centre, however, do not portray this unique characteristic.

Mucobe, spikes

All the huts at Riuki Cultural Centre including the *ikumbi* are finished with a *mucobe* at the exterior apex of the roof. This is highly reminiscent of the traditional form of the Agikuyu huts.

The roof

The roof constructed at Riuki consists of a bed of bracken fern laid onto the wooden rafters as in fig. Hoops have been tied around the rafters to support the framework. This closely resembles the traditional roof which consists of wooden rafters and hoops as in fig.

Fig. 4.106; The roof at Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.102; An image of the *githaku* at Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.104; The *mucobe* at Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.103; The roof at Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.105; An image of the *githaku* in a traditional homestead. Source: agefoto.com, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.107; The *mucobe* on a traditional hut. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.108; The traditional roof. Source: Kamenju J., 2013

USE OF SPACE

The Nja
Storytelling

Fig shows the debris of a storytelling session after an event the foreigners attended. The fire is lit at the centre of the space. The people are seated on the logs around it. Traditionally, this layout mimics the grandfather seated around the fire with the grandchildren while telling them stories as in fig.

This type of layout resembles the Ubuntu concept and brings the users of this space together and even more intimate.

Dancing

At Riuki, a group of dancers make their way towards a performance hall in a line as the visitors sit on the logs of wood that act as the seats. The dances are therefore performed for the visitors. In the traditional layout as in fig., the dancers perform the dances for themselves. The position of the spectators on the outer edges of the circle of dancers showcases their unimportance in this rite of passage. The dance would have still gone on if there was one or none of the spectators. In the modern scenario as in Riuki Cultural Centre, these dances would not happen if the visitors did not avail themselves. The circular and more organic arrangement of the traditional dance starts assuming a more orthogonal spatial layout in the modern performance.

Fig. 4.110; Image of a storytelling debris. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.111; Image of the performance area. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.114; Spatial arrangement of Riuki's performance area. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.109; Image of a storytelling session in a traditional context. Source: pinterest.com, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.112; Image of the traditional performance area. Source: Il Popolo Kikuyu, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.113; Spatial arrangement of the traditional performance area. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

MATERIALS

At Riuki Cultural Centre, the traditional huts showcase the use of traditional materials such as mud, reed and wood with respect to the traditional hut in fig. The caretaker's hut in fig. displays the use of modern materials such as concrete used in the masonry wall. The use of corrugated iron sheets in place of grass or reed is a good attempt to reinterpret the traditional Agikuyu architecture in the modern context. The introduction of the metallic gutter to facilitate collection of rainwater is an even better

In as much as most of the huts are used for showcase, the visitor can be able to appreciate the traditional from the modern hut. However, some of the visitors from Nairobi wished that the huts would have been converted for accommodation purposes. Karia is a very small rural town that is far from the capital and enjoying the Riuki experience would have been more profitable if the visitors had a longer stay and not a rushed visit. This is because most of them have to go back home after the visit. For those looking for a day out of their hustle and bustle lives in the capital, then Riuki should have been more open to offer this experience. This would attract more visitors, including the Gikuyu people, to enjoy this experience. The huts are in a poor state and are thus not habitable.

Fig. 4.115; An image of materials used for a hut in Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.117; Materials used at Riuki for the caretaker's hut. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 4.116; Materials used in a traditional hut. Source: Kamenju J., 2013

**5.0 CHAPTER
FIVE:
CONCLUSIONS AND
RECOMMENDATIONS**

Fig. 5.01; A traditional homestead. Source: [pinterest.com](https://www.pinterest.com) retrieved in Dec. 2019

Fig. 5.02; Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's house in Limuru. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

5.1 Introduction

This final chapter concludes the purpose of this thesis; the Agikuyu architecture restatement. From the earlier chapters, the author has been able to answer the research questions that bore the need of this study. Chapter two has taken into account how spaces and forms are created. This chapter went on to narrow down this study to the Agikuyu people in an effort to understand how their beliefs, customs and practices, as well as the earlier discussed factors that determine space and form making, contributed to how they built their environment to suit their cultural needs (Fig. 5.01). The ‘*How did Agikuyu practices and traditions factor in the generation of spaces and forms?*’ question was then answered. This question enlightened the author with what type of spaces and forms the Agikuyu created and what purposes they served. After this chapter, the author devised the following parameters; spatial layout, form, use of space and the materials used. These variables were then used to compare the traditional Agikuyu forms and spaces with the modern, yet restated, Agikuyu forms and spaces in the fourth chapter of this thesis. These restatements were Riuki Cultural Centre in Kiambu, Ngugi Wa Thiong’o’s house in Limuru (Fig. 5.02) and Thingira Cultural Village in Sagana.

Chapter Four has in part set precedence in meeting the final objective of this study: *To establish successful and failed attempts made to reinterpret traditional Agikuyu spaces and forms.* In the previous chapter, the author has looked into the efforts made by the centres mentioned above in reinterpreting traditional Agikuyu architecture. This chapter will look into whether they were successful or failed in doing so. For those that have failed, the author will propose what could have been done to ensure they would have attained success in the interpretation of the Agikuyu traditional architecture.

Fig. 5.03; The traditional hut. Source: Author, Dec. 2019

Fig. 5.04; The hut at Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Dec. 2019

5.2 Case study one: Thingira Cultural Village, Sagana

5.21 Conclusions

For each of the variables, the following conclusions were made:

5.211 Spatial Layout

It was a good attempt in the interpretation of the traditional Agikuyu spatial layout. The sons' *thingiras* are located closest to the entrance as in the traditional context. The order of *kihingo*, *thome* and then *nja* were maintained. In addition, the *mucii*, homestead, had two entrances and exits typical of some of the traditional *mucii*.

5.212 The form

Higher floor-to-ceiling heights have been achieved at Thingira Cultural Village as in fig. 5.04. This is in opposition to the very low floor-to-ceiling heights of the traditional *nyumba*, fig. 5.03, that necessitated the average man to bend in order to access it. It is worth mentioning the effort taken to consider the human scale. To further support this, the *muromo*, doorway, allowance is bigger and the man can comfortably access it contrary to its traditional equivalent.

Lack of the *githaku*, entrance porch, is not a good feature as it is still an important spatial element even in these modern times. It acts as a transitioning and storage space. This could be because no residents live within the *mucii* and therefore do not appreciate its need.

The lack of the *muikio*, the flying beam, is also a huge disappointment. The *muikio* was a very distinct feature in the form of the *nyumba* and should have been maintained.

The roof's thickness has greatly reduced.

5.213 Use of space

Most of the activities performed in the *nja*, courtyard, have been maintained but used for cultural education of the visitors. The spatial arrangement of these cultural education practices at Thingira closely resembles the layout of the traditional *gichukia* dance, a traditional cultural education

Fig. 5.05; An image of Thingira Cultural Village. Source: Author, Dec. 2019

Fig. 5.06; An image of a theatre. Source: www.teatrocircoprice.es retrieved in Dec. 2019

Fig. 5.07; A building built using modern materials. Source: architizer.com downloaded in Dec. 2019

practice. The importance of the circle as a spatial design element in Agikuyu traditions is showcased in these dances.

5.214 Materials

The materials used in the design of the huts at Thingira are a mimic of those used in the traditional huts as in fig. 5.05. No interpretation has been achieved by the designer. This is because no modern materials such as steel or glass have been used. Constructed in 2012, the building thus loses a place in its time.

With these conclusions, the author deems the attempts made unsuccessful. Nevertheless, no one resides in this space. Visitors who use the space only do so for a limited amount of time. As a result, it loses its realism. The author therefore proposes the following recommendations to improve the situation:

5.22 Recommendations

The introduction of the farm around the homestead.

The revival of the *githaku* and the *muikio*.

Introduction of a more organic inner fence.

Creation of indoor spaces such as theatre, fig. 5.06, for performances as the rain would hinder cultural education practices.

Use modern materials, fig. 5.07, to place the building in its historical time.

5.3 Case study two: Ngugi wa Thiong'o's house, Limuru

5.31 Conclusions

The conclusions made are discussed below as per the variables:

5.311 Spatial Layout

The architect made a remarkable effort in laying out most spaces in Ngugi's compound in line with the traditional homestead. For instance, the positioning of the farm around the residence to provide food and income for his family. The Agikuyu people were and are still agriculturalists to this day. The provision of such a space is therefore imperative as it ensures their survival today as well as maintains a link to their past.

In the traditional context, the major spaces are laid out at the centre of the plot while the minor spaces surround them as in fig. 5.08. The minor spaces at Ngugi's are the farm, garbage heap and the borehole which act as servant spaces to the major living space as in fig. 5.09.

The provision of the *kihingo*, *thome* and *nja* in that subsequent order is a great achievement by the architect. Traditionally, these spaces served important purposes. They are still as useful today. The *kihingo* is the gate nowadays. It ensures protection from outside forces. The *thome* is still a large area used to welcome the visitors. Parking is mostly located in this space. The *nja* is the central space that acts as the datum to the establishment.

The lounge space is a great modern addition to the design of the modern Agikuyu house.

Traditionally, this space was never considered as most spaces were mainly functional and rarely for luxurious purposes.

All the spaces have been merged into one house. The house accommodates the father, mother, sons and daughters and even guests. The consideration of gender as a space and form making

Fig. 5.08; Spatial layout of a traditional homestead. Source: Author, Dec. 2019

Fig. 5.0910; Spatial layout of Ngugi's residence. Source: Author, Dec. 2019

Fig. 5.11; A granary at Thingira Cultural Village.
Source: Author, Sept. 2019

Fig. 5.121; An image of a study room. Source:
pinterest.com retrieved in Dec. 2019

determinant has been abandoned. Traditionally, the Agikuyu men and women lived in separate huts. In Ngugi's residence, they all live together in one house.

Study rooms, fig. 5.11, are the modern 'granaries'. Occupational changes have led to the loss of granaries, fig. 5.10, in the modern era. Ngugi, being a professor of literature, provides for his family through educating others on the knowledge he has attained by reading the books in his study room. Agriculture has then come second as an occupation and used as a back-up plan. The abandonment of the square and the circle as a design principle of the interior spatial layout.

5.312 The Form

The entrance path, *kihingo*, is wider to accommodate the motor vehicle. Its character mimics the traditional one as they are both enclosed on the upper levels by long branches of trees or sticks. One can hardly view the entirety of the celestial dome from this space. This forms an umbrella-like and a grove-like tunnel as the entry path.

Higher floor-to-ceiling heights have been achieved. This is in consideration to the human scale and comfort.

The provision of the *githaku* as a transitioning space from the *nja* to the interior spaces is a great effort by the architect.

The provision of the ceiling board is a poor restatement to the traditional Agikuyu architecture. This is because it conceals the roof framework of the Agikuyu huts which was very distinctive. The *muikio*, if considered, cannot be viewed.

Merging the flat roof and the conical pitched roof represents the new and the old, the modern and the traditional: the restatement of the traditional in the modern times. The flat roof connects the three huts assumed by the three conical pitched roofs. Through observation, one cannot differentiate the *nyumba* from the *thingira*. The *nyumba* was always bigger in size than the

Fig. 5.132; The square and the circle design concept in the spatial organization of the traditional Agikuyu *nyumba*. Source: Author, Dec. 2019

thingira. The three huts differ in size by only 3 feet. This difference in size is not great enough to visually pick out the *nyumba* from the *thingira*.

5.313 Use of space

The *nja* still serves the same purposes at Ngugi's and in the traditional context. It is still used for relaxing and drying grains.

5.314 Materials

A great attempt of giving the building a place in its time was made by the architect. Use of glass, concrete, wood, plastic, steel, brick among other modern materials contributed to this.

Modern materials serve functional and aesthetic purposes. Traditional materials serve only functional purposes. Cladding is a modern building technology. In the Agikuyu traditional context, materials were used to ensure comfort and safety and rarely to be eye-appealing.

All in all, the author deems the attempts made successful. For a building built in 1974 and currently housing the second generation of the family, the architect accomplished a difficult task in reinterpreting traditional Agikuyu architecture.

5.32 Recommendations

The revival of the square and the circle design concept should have been considered. The combination of these shapes was a distinct characteristic of the traditional Agikuyu architecture as fig. 5.12. This would have immensely guided the architect in the interior spatial design which was done poorly. Some of the wall meet at acute angles proving difficult for the internal arrangement of standardized modern furniture.

Fig. 5.143; The gatehouse, a modern interpretation of the sons' thingira. Source: parkutinternational.com, Dec. 2019

Fig. 5.164; Wider entrances to accommodate the motor vehicle. Source: fenceokc.com, Dec. 2019

5.4 Case study three: Riuki Cultural Centre, Kiambu

5.41 Conclusions

5.411 Spatial Layout

The spatial layout at Riuki closely resembles the traditional *mucii* layout. From the farm surrounding the residence to the central *nja* as the datum, it is a good attempt on the part of the designer.

The interpretation of the traditional sons' thingira located close to the entrance to the gatehouse is an even greater attempt. Since the culture nowadays allows for young men to live in their father's house, the hut closest to the gate was interpreted to a gatehouse, fig. 5.13. Basically, this is a modern intervention as the guards residing in the gatehouse represent the Agikuyu young men living closest to the entrance guarding the *mucii*.

Provision of spaces that are not habitable is a poor attempt. No one resides in all the huts except the caretaker's one. The granaries do not store any grains from the farm.

5.412 The Form

Entrances are open to sky unlike its traditional counterpart which was always covered by greenery or sticks. The grove-like entrance has been neglected.

Higher floor-to-ceiling heights than the traditional huts have been achieved.

Wider entrance paths, fig. 5.14, and doorway allowances to accommodate the motor vehicle and the man respectively.

Lack of the *githaku*, entrance porch, in the design of the nyumba.

Similar sizes of the traditional nyumba and thingira to the ones at Riuki Cultural Centre.

Fig. 5.175; The spatial arrangement of a storytelling session around a fire. Source: Author, Dec. 2019

Fig. 5.186; A hut at Riuki Cultural Centre. Source: Author, Sept. 2019

5.413 Use of space

The circular and more organic traditional spatial arrangement of the dances has been interpreted to a more orthogonal layout as witnessed at Riuki Cultural Centre.

Performances are no longer for the dancers as it were traditionally, but for the spectators in the modern context. Spectators are given more priority at Riuki. In the traditional dance, the spectators were not part of the dance. The dance would have still happened without their presence.

The fire-making debris at Riuki mimics the old storytelling sessions. In both cases, the fire is at the centre and the people sit around it as in fig. 5.15. These spaces promote cultural education practices in form of stories, riddles, folktales etc.

In conclusion, the circle is a powerful tool in promoting cultural education practices.

5.414 Materials

No modern materials such as glass, steel or concrete have been used. This is a poor modern restatement on the part of the designer.

The traditional materials are chipping out due to poor maintenance by the owners. As in fig. 5.16, the huts look unattractive and uninviting to visitors especially from the Agikuyu community.

For a development that was built to invite its people, it has terribly failed to do so. While interviewing some of the Agikuyu people living around Riuki, most of them did not find the place attractive. They figured it was designed for the foreigners who found the place pretty interesting. For the interviewees, it was nothing new. It was nothing they haven't seen. It was nothing they wanted to see. And it was definitely nothing they will ever want to see.

As a result, the efforts made were unsuccessful.

Fig. 5.197; An illustration of the spatial layout of a Gikuyu traditional dance. Source: Author, Dec. 2019

5.42 Recommendations

The author would like to propose the following recommendations:

Use of more modern materials as they are aesthetically pleasing and would attract the Agikuyu people.

Provide more habitable spaces such as accommodation for the visitors who come from far.

Revive the circular and more organic traditional spatial arrangement of the dances as illustrated in fig. 5.17.

Design an indoor space for these cultural education practices.

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